

Symbiosis of smart objects across IoT environments

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2nd Open Call text and Submission Template

The symbloTe Consortium

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1 Executive Summary

The deliverable D6.2 “2nd Open Call Text and Submission Template” is the second deliverable planned for Work Package 6 “Open Calls”. This document outlines the procedures and objectives planned for managing the symbloTe Second Open Call, which will be publicly announced on 31st October 2017 with deadline for submission on 31st January 2018.

This document defines the main structure of the procedure for managing the second Open Call and represents the core content to be used as the supporting documentation for the launch of the public announcement.

The context of the sections have been prepared in order to give a complete overview about the procedure planned and legal terms and conditions ruling the Cascade Funding (art. 15 – symbloTe Grant Agreement), such as:

- Open Call Summary
- Open Call Technical Details
- Applicant’s Guide
- Eligibility Criteria
- Confidentiality and Conflict of Interest Declaration for External Experts
- Evaluation Criteria
- symbloTe Standard Extension Contract
- Technical report template
- Specific Extension Contract
- Grant Agreement Specific Obligations for Third Parties

2 Introduction

2.1 *Purpose of the document*

This deliverable D6.2 “2nd Open Call Text and Submission Template” reports the procedure set up for carrying out the second symbloTe Open Call. The information reported consists of all the necessary contents for preparing further materials to be published and distributed for advertising the launch of the open call.

This deliverable gives the general information on what the second Open Call background and objectives are, as well as on the application process and support services provided by the symbloTe consortium. The document sketches also the dissemination channels which will be exploited for attracting submissions and enlarging the Call’s impact. All the call documents and related materials are subjected to changes and updates during the implementation phase which will bring to the launch of the call, planned for M22 (end of October 2017). Nonetheless, the modification and changes that may occur will be just minor with respect to the core presented here and will concern procedural details and updates in the legal documents. However, all the information and any updates will be published on the dedicated page of symbloTe web site early before the launch of the Call

The general structure, adopted by symbloTe consortium for carrying out the two rounds of the Open calls, has been sketched following recommendation advised by IoT-EPI during the Vienna Meeting (10th – 13th October 2016) and it reflects the harmonization decision taken among all the Cluster projects.

Regarding the submission procedure, based on the positive experience of the First Open call, the F6S platform will be again used as the submission platform to automate the proposal submission and evaluation procedures.

To attract high quality applications and maximize the outreach of the call, a set of dissemination activities will be organized, so that the symbloTe Open Call will also be advertised through different channels. The details about the documents, the information days and advertising plans will be given in Section 7.

This document further provides information for applicants on what to expect during the implementation phase if their proposal is successful and selected for funding (Agreement with the Coordinator, Payment on reported work, and support services from the Consortium).

The documents planned for the public announcement, which will be produced during the implementation phase and will give guidance for applicants, will be:

- Open Call Summary
- Open Call Technical Details
- Applicant’s Guide
- Eligibility Criteria
- Confidentiality and Conflict of Interest Declaration for External Experts
- Evaluation Criteria
- symbloTe Standard Extension Contract
- Technical report template
- Specific Extension Contract

2.2 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable first gives an summary of the symbloTe 2nd Open Call. It then provide more technical details on the scope of each topic. Moreover, it outlines the Open Call procedures and support services offered to the applicants by the symbloTe Consortium. The document then lays out in more detail what a potential partner could expect if the proposal is selected for funding, in terms of access to project IPR, reporting, support during the implementation and payment schedule on performed work.

The main information related to the second symbloTe Open call management is included the in the next sections as follows:

Section 3 provides a summary of the 2nd Open Call, by briefly introducing the concepts of symbloTe and describing the five (5) different topics of the Open Call, along with short information about funding and number of submissions to be funded per topic.

Section 4 describes the Technical Details of the 3rd Open Call. Initially, the overall symbloTe approach is described and the different aspects of IoT interoperability are presented, along with the matching symbloTe solution. Then, for each topic of the 2nd Open Call, a more detailed description of what the applicants are expected to implement when accepted is provided, along with the funding details and the targeted type of applicants.

Section 5 highlights the Application procedure set up for the second Open Call, by providing a walkthrough for the symbloTe's web site, where all necessary material is available, and for the F6S submission platform, so that applicants can easily get acquainted with the submission procedure and the information expected to be provided in the submission form.

Section 6 provides some additional details about the 2nd Open Call, such as deadlines, the eligibility criteria, the supporting services to applicants and the funding conditions, the expected duration of the commitment by the selected applicants, as well as any legal issues related to relationship between selected Third Parties and the symbloTe consortium.

Section 7 describes the overall communication activities addressed to raise awareness on Open call for attracting Third Parties and the specific material to be produced. It describes also the supporting services that will be deployed for assisting applicants in the preparation of the proposal.

Section 8 gives an overview of the Evaluation procedures set up for symbloTe Open Calls and the Evaluation Criteria.

Section 9 describes the process after an applicant is selected: the contracts to be prepared, the support during the implementation of their project, the paying scheme, the reporting to be made and the involved IPR issues.

Finally, the Appendices contain the main documents already prepared for implementing the Open Call procedure: the symbloTe Standard Extension Contract (and its annexes; subject to slight modification prior to the launch of the call), as well as the Confidentiality and Conflict of Interest Declaration for the External Evaluators.

3 Summary of the 2nd Open Call

In this section, we provide a summary for symbloTe's 2nd Open Call, which helps the interested parties to quickly understand the goals of symbloTe and the targets of its 2nd Open Call.

3.1 Introducing symbloTe

symbloTe is an H2020 Research and Innovation Action and member of the [IoT-European Platforms Initiative](#) cluster that addresses a challenging objective of creating an interoperable IoT ecosystem. symbloTe will facilitate the cooperation of vertical IoT platforms, which are today typically offered as closed systems, to simplify the development of cross-domain and cross-platform IoT applications. Within the 2nd Open Call, **symbloTe is seeking for proposals from legal entities that are developing their own proprietary or open source solutions falling into the category of IoT platforms or IoT applications, as well as user communities available to participate in symbloTe trials in mid-2018.**

Why symbloTe? The need for cross-domain IoT applications that can cover multiple aspects of everyday life is becoming more apparent nowadays. Therefore, in order to shape the future with more collaborative experiences, vertically isolated platforms need to be extended in order to cover other domains in which, however, the companies may not have the required expertise. Strategic partnerships are expected to be the only viable option, especially for start-ups and SMEs. Moreover, the collocation of IoT platforms may result in resource inefficiencies, since similar sensors may happen to be deployed by different platforms at the same location. Furthermore, the burden of a single stakeholder deploying and managing the end-to-end infrastructure, from sensors and gateways to back-office servers and platforms, introduces a very high cost and skill barrier for new entrants to the IoT market which may, in turn, hold back the innovation opportunities for SMEs and start-ups. symbloTe comes to remedy this fragmented environment by 'bridging IoT islands' with an abstraction layer for a 'unified view' on various platforms and their devices/services so that platform resources become transparent to application designers and developers.

Our Vision. symbloTe is creating an *interoperability framework* to enable IoT platforms to open up access to their devices/services in a controlled and secure manner, aiming to acquire new revenue streams for offering added value services but also to receive missing ingredients that will enrich their business offerings. symbloTe is not ‘yet another IoT platform’, as it is not designed to store any sensor-generated data, but rather a mediator facilitating the exchange of the necessary metadata that describe the exposed IoT devices/services. Thus, symbloTe provides the required software infrastructure to find and allow for unified and secure access to the necessary IoT devices/services for third party platform owners and application developers.

Open platform interfaces come as a response to the emerging need for cross-domain IoT applications and services. By leveraging symbloTe interfaces, developed components and libraries, IoT platforms will be able to offer unified and secure access to their sensors and actuators. The devices remain under full control of platform developers and owners, who define and manage access rights to their infrastructure. On the one hand, this will support application developers to rapidly create and deploy novel IoT applications without the need to own and operate the IoT infrastructure. On the other hand, IoT platform providers and infrastructure owners will be able to increase their user/developer base and create new revenue streams, since their infrastructure is used in innovative cross-domain applications. This will create a vibrant IoT ecosystem with potential to create new business cases for existing IoT stakeholders.

Our Approach. The main goal of symbloTe is to devise a flexible and secure interoperability middleware across IoT platforms facilitating rapid development of IoT applications across platforms, platform collaborations as well as dynamic and adaptive smart objects and environments. This is accomplished by a series of innovations introduced by symbloTe. The first innovation refers to building an IoT search engine for connected (virtualized) smart objects (i.e., IoT resources), where IoT platform providers can register their deployed resources and other platforms/applications can search and access them. The second innovation involves an abstraction layer for unified and secure usage of those resources across platforms. A third key ingredient is to implement high-level, domain-specific APIs (“domain enablers”) for rapid cross-platform application development. A fourth new feature that symbloTe introduces is the support for IoT platform federations, i.e., associations between two platforms facilitating their secure interaction, collaboration and bartering of resources. The fifth innovative aspect of symbloTe is to create dynamic and self-configurable smart spaces through the seamless blending of next generation mobile devices with surrounding environments and host platforms. Finally, all the above are facilitated through a secure interworking protocol between the IoT platforms, gateways and smart devices.

Our Use Cases. The symbloTe use cases aim at showcasing the introduced innovations and how they can assist people seamlessly while performing their everyday, indoor and outdoor, activities. These environments can range from homes, offices and public spaces (e.g. campuses, stadiums or ports), to smart mobility solutions that assist travellers and commuters. The diversity of the considered environments is optimal to showcase platform interoperability, since it spans over a number of various IoT implementations, which are currently isolated and managed as closed systems. In contrast to the current situation, when a user has to use different applications at home, for public transport, at the university, etc., symbloTe use cases will demonstrate a completely new type of applications built on top of interoperable platforms. The following use cases are developed within symbloTe:

- *Smart residence* aims to demonstrate interoperability across different smart home IoT solutions through a generalized abstract model to describe inter-connected objects, providing a dynamic configuration of available services and a natural and homogeneous user experience.
- *Smart campus* develops "eduroam-like" IoT services for visiting students and staff to offer indoor navigation and room/equipment booking.
- *Smart stadium* uses indoor location platforms to be integrated with various context-based information services so that, e.g., visitors can receive promotions on services/products offered in the stadium, as well as perform remote ordering.
- *Smart mobility and ecological urban routing* aims at addressing the problem of inefficient transport and poor air quality that many European cities face nowadays by tracking citizen exposure to pollutants and offering 'green' routes for bicyclists and pedestrians. In addition to in-situ stations, it uses wearable sensors and mobile devices for air quality monitoring.
- *Smart yachting* automates the exchange of information between a boat and the port, operated by two different platforms.

3.2 Overview of 2nd Open Call

With this Open Call, symbloTe aims to enlarge the number of symbloTe-enabled IoT platforms that wish to become a tangible part of an evolving IoT ecosystem. We are seeking for legal entities that are developing their own or extending open source solutions falling into the category of IoT platforms. It is expected that an IoT platform joining the symbloTe ecosystem can be used in domains relevant to symbloTe use cases, in particular Smart Residence/Office/Building/Campus and Smart Cities (including mobility and citizen involvement).

Selected applicants will work on projects (we call them "Extensions") and focus on extending their IoT platforms so as 1) to integrate an open interface defined by symbloTe with the platform, 2) to integrate the symbloTe solution for authentication and authorization with the platform and 3) to support registration of selected devices managed by the platform with external symbloTe services. Note that a platform-specific information model needs to be aligned with the symbloTe-specific information model during this process. The applicants are expected to adopt the respective innovations introduced by symbloTe that matches their business needs and domains. These innovations are referred as "symbloTe compliance levels" and are further explained in the Technical Documentation of this Open Call.

Moreover, the applicants need to show potential to deploy the developed solution so as to open up access to a selected subset of IoT devices under applicant's administrative control to the symbloTe ecosystem. The applicant's ability to test symbloTe services in real life settings will be considered an asset. In addition, the applicants will be requested to enrich the symbloTe trials, which are planned at the same period when the Extensions will run, by offering their IoT resources as well to be used within symbloTe trials.

The symbloTe consortium will provide the definition of platform interface(s) together with a set of software components providing an implementation of the interface(s) accompanying libraries and plugin components to ease the process of integrating symbloTe features for interoperability with existing platform implementations. The symbloTe consortium will

provide support and guidance during the learning, design and integration phases of the Extensions. The symbloTe consortium is developing open source software using a business-friendly license so that proprietary IoT platforms, which become symbloTe-enabled, remain proprietary.

At the following table, we provide the summary of the topics active in this 2nd Open Call. The first three topics focus on making IoT platforms symbloTe-complaint. The fourth topic searches for application developers to build innovative mobile apps on top of symbloTe. The last topic looks for end users to support symbloTe's planned trials.

Table: Summary of 2nd Open Call topics

Topic Identifier	Topic Description	Type of Applicants	Funding
symbloTe-OC2-L1	<p>Purpose: To make 3rd party IoT platforms L1-compliant, so that they expose IoT resources to the symbloTe Core Services. Applicants should offer platforms active in the Smart City domain, involving (but not limited to) city-wide IoT platforms for environmental monitoring, traffic/parking monitoring, mobility aspects, etc.</p> <p>Commitment: Applicants should make their platforms and their resources available for a demo during the symbloTe trials (mid/end 2018).</p>	IoT Platform owners / operators	<p>Up to €40,000 per Extension</p> <p>Approx. two (2) Extensions to be funded</p>
symbloTe-OC2-L2	<p>Purpose: To make 3rd party IoT platforms L2-compliant, so that they join platform federations. Applicants should explicitly mention with which symbloTe platforms they would like to federate with (see list of available platforms at the end of this topic) and what could be the business value out of this federation. A desired feature would be that apart from making their IoT platform L2-compliant, they also extend their native apps to display/access/control federated resources.</p> <p>Commitment: Applicants should make their platforms and their resources available during the symbloTe demos and trials (mid/end 2018).</p>	IoT Platform owners / operators	<p>Up to €50,000 per Extension</p> <p>Approx. four (4) Extensions to be funded</p>
symbloTe-OC2-L3/4	<p>Purpose: To make 3rd party IoT gateways and/or IP native families of devices L3/4-compliant. The proposed Extensions must include at least 10 devices of at least 3 different types. Such devices can be: i) gateway-controlled devices, ii) IP-native smart devices or iii) a mix of the previous.</p> <p>Commitment: Applicants must join a challenge event (end 2018) to demonstrate</p>	IoT Gateway and/or IP native device manufacturers, system integrators	<p>Up to €40,000 per Extension</p> <p>Approx. four (4) Extensions to be funded</p>

	their solution and to pass a set of symbloTe-defined interoperability tests.		
symbloTe-OC2-Apps	<p>Purpose: To build a smart phone application (Android or iOS) that combines resources offered by L1-compliant platforms and/or available Domain Enablers and demonstrates cross-domain features. Proposed applications should focus in the domains of Smart City, Smart Residence and Smart Stadium/Buildings, as well as combination of the above.</p> <p>Commitment: Applicants should make their applications available for a demo during the symbloTe trials (mid/end 2018).</p>	Mobile app companies	<p>Up to €20,000 per Extension</p> <p>Approx. three (3) Extensions to be funded</p>
symbloTe-OC2-Trials	<p>Purpose: To involve end users and citizens that will use our applications and hardware (portable sensors, etc) to support our "Smart Mobility and Ecological Urban Routing" trial.</p> <p>Commitment: Support the trials planned in Zagreb, Vienna and Porto (mid/end 2018).</p>	NGOs, municipalities, organizations, companies with end users in Zagreb, Vienna and Porto.	<p>Up to €15,000 per Extension</p> <p>Approx. three (3) Extensions to be funded</p>

4 Technical Details of the 2nd Open Call

In this section, we go into more details about the symbloTe approach and the Open Call topics. The purpose is to help interested parties understand the specificities of the symbloTe approach for IoT interoperability, the designed architecture and implemented prototype, as well as the requirements of each Open Call topic.

4.1 The symbloTe Approach

symbloTe addresses a challenging objective to create an interoperable Internet of Things (IoT) ecosystem that will allow for the collaboration of vertical IoT platforms towards the creation of cross-domain applications. Thus, it designs an *interoperable mediation framework* to enable the discovery and sharing of connected devices across existing and future IoT platforms for rapid development of cross-platform IoT applications. symbloTe allows for *flexible interoperability mechanisms* which can be achieved by introducing an incremental deployment of symbloTe functionality across the platform's space, which will in effect influence the level of platform collaboration and cooperation with other platforms within a symbloTe-enabled IoT ecosystem. Syntactic and semantic interoperability represent the essential mechanisms in the future symbloTe-enabled ecosystem, while organizational interoperability has different flavors within symbloTe (platform federations, dynamic Smart Spaces and roaming IoT devices) to enable platform providers to choose an adequate interoperability model for their business needs.

The symbloTe approach defines **four interoperability levels**. We also refer to them as **compliance levels**, when considering them from the perspective of an IoT platform wanting to become interoperable. In all four levels, interoperability is achieved by offering a unified and secure way to advertise, discover and consume IoT resources, but in each level a different interoperability scenario is enabled offering various degrees of details about the involved resources.

Figure 1: L1 compliance: application-to-resource

Figure 2: L2 compliance: platform-to-platform

Level 1 (L1) enables interactions between IoT applications and virtualized IoT resources, i.e., third party applications or systems can find and use resources across platforms through uniform interfaces. This is accomplished by the symbloTe Core Services which

allow IoT platforms to register and advertise their offered resources. At the same time, platforms can integrate symbloTe components to offer uniform and secure access to their virtualized resources. Level 1 can be considered as a search engine for IoT resources.

Level 2 (L2) allows IoT platforms to closely collaborate by forming federations. Federations can be considered as a closed and distributed version of the Core services, i.e., the platforms can advertise only to the members of the federation the resources they want to make available and such resources can be discovered and used only by members of the federations. The operation of IoT federations is governed by employed trust and resource bartering mechanisms.

Figure 3: L3 compliance: IoT device-to-IoT device

Figure 4: L4 compliance: roaming IoT device-to-smart space

Level 3 (L3) enables dynamic smart spaces, i.e., the adoption of new resources at the gateway level and the direct interactions between symbloTe-enabled IoT devices (e.g. mobile devices and Arduino boards) which are collocated in smart spaces, even if they are connected to different gateways and managed by different IoT platforms. This enables resource migration between collocated and in proximity IoT gateways and prevents vendor lock-in.

Level 4 (L4) offers support for roaming of IoT devices (e.g. smartphones and wearables) to interact with smart objects within a visited smart space managed by an IoT platform. A roaming device maintains its unique identity while on the move, and can interact with a smart space only in case the involved IoT platforms are collaborating.

4.2 *symbloTe*: Technical Details

4.2.1 The symbloTe Architecture

The symbloTe architecture is built around a layered IoT stack connecting various devices (sensors, actuators and IoT gateways) within Smart Spaces with the Cloud. Smart Spaces share the available local resources (connectivity, computing and storage), while platform services running in the Cloud will enable IoT Platform Federations (associations between two platforms) and open up the Interworking Interface¹ to third parties. The architecture

¹ Interworking Interface is a symbloTe defined interface which opens up platform resources as IoT Services in the Cloud Domain.

comprises four layered domains, 1) Application Domain, 2) Cloud Domain, 3) Smart Space Domain and 4) Device Domain, as depicted in Figure 5. Hereafter we list the main functional objectives for each of these domains:

Application Domain (APP): enables platforms to register IoT devices which they want to advertise and make accessible via symbloTe to third parties, while symbloTe provides the means for discovery of IoT devices across platforms by its Core Services. Domain-specific back-end services (called 'Domain Enablers') are envisioned to be placed in APP: they utilize the infrastructure provided by the underlying platforms to offer value-added services, e.g. data analytics on top of sensor data acquired from different platforms, which can ease the process of cross-platform and domain-specific application development (specifically for mobile and web applications).

Cloud Domain (CLD): provides a uniform and secure access to virtualized IoT devices exposed by platforms to third parties through an open API (Interworking Interface). In addition, it builds services for IoT Platform Federations enabling direct platform collaboration, in accordance with platform-specific business rules.

Figure 5: The symbloTe high-level architecture

Smart Space Domain (SSP): provides services for discovery and registration of new IoT devices in dynamic local smart spaces, dynamic configuration of devices in accordance with predefined policies in those environments, and well-documented interfaces for devices available in smart spaces.

Smart Device Domain (SDEV): relates to smart devices and their roaming capabilities. We assume that devices have the capabilities to blend with a surrounding smart space while they are on the move. In other words, smart devices can interact with devices in a visited smart space, which are managed by a visited platform, in accordance with predefined access policies.

4.2.2 Interoperability Aspects

symbloTe allows for flexible interoperability mechanisms which can be achieved by introducing an incremental deployment of symbloTe functionality across the listed domains (APP, CLD, SSP and SDEV). This approach will enable platform providers to choose an appropriate level of integration of symbloTe-specific services within their platforms, which will, in effect, influence the level of platform collaboration and cooperation with other platforms within a symbloTe-enabled ecosystem. For example, a platform may only choose to expose its Interworking Interface and selected IoT services to third parties in order to advertise them by using the symbloTe Core Services, or it may opt for a closer collaboration with another platform by forming a platform federation. Platform federations require additional symbloTe components to be included and integrated within a platform space in CLD.

Figure 6: symbloTe Compliance Levels

We define four different Compliance Levels (CLs) for IoT platforms, as depicted in Figure 6. They reflect different interoperability modes, which an IoT platform can support. Different interoperability modes affect the functionality which needs to be supported by symbloTe-enabled platforms, and require specific symbloTe components to be integrated within different domains.

Level 1 (L1) Compliant Platform: This is a "lightweight" symbloTe CL since a platform opens up only its Interworking Interface to third parties to advertise and offer its virtualized IoT devices through the symbloTe Core Services. It enables the syntactic and semantic interoperability of IoT platforms in a symbloTe ecosystem, and affects only APP and CLD.

Level 2 (L2) Compliant Platform: This level assumes that platforms federate, which requires additional functionality to be included in CLD, for example for sharing/bartering of devices, as well as managing federated credentials. The functionality provided at this level enables the so-called organizational interoperability.

Level 3 (L3) Compliant Platform: This CL assumes that platforms integrate symbloTe components within their smart spaces to simplify the integration and dynamic reconfiguration of IoT devices within local spaces.

Level 4 (L4) Compliant Platform: This level offers support for device roaming and can enable the interaction of smart devices which maintain their unique identity (L4 devices) with a visited smart space. A prerequisite for this interaction is that the smart space is already Level 3 compliant, so that smart spaces can discover visiting L4 devices and integrate them (e.g., grant access to certain local resources). Note that an L4 device may

be registered either with symbloTe Core Services or within a platform federation, and thus its new location and visited smart space should be updated (the idea is conceptually similar to Mobile IP).

4.3 OC2: Detailed description of topics

The topics of the symbloTe's 2nd Open Call (OC2) are summarized as follows:

Topic Identifier	Targeted Applicants	Funding
symbloTe-OC2-L1	IoT platform owners/operators	≤ €40,000
symbloTe-OC2-L2	IoT platform owners/operators	≤ €50,000
symbloTe-OC2-L3/4	IoT gateway manufacturers, Smart device manufacturers, integrators	≤ €40,000
symbloTe-OC2-Apps	Mobile application companies	≤ €20,000
symbloTe-OC2-Trials	NGOs, Municipalities, SMEs engaging user communities	≤ €15,000

The first three topics focus on making IoT platforms symbloTe-compliant. The fourth topic searches for application developers to build innovative mobile apps on top of symbloTe. The last topic looks for end users to support symbloTe's planned trials. In the pages that follow we provide a detailed description for each topic.

4.3.1 symbloTe-OC2-L1

Topic Summary

Purpose: To make 3rd party IoT platforms L1-compliant, so that they expose IoT resources to the symbloTe Core Services. Applicants should offer platforms active in the Smart City domain, involving (but not limited to) city-wide IoT platforms for environmental monitoring, traffic/parking monitoring, mobility aspects, etc.

Commitment: Applicants should make their platforms and their resources available for a demo during the symbloTe trials (mid/end 2018).

Type of Applicants: IoT Platform owners / operators

Funding: up to €40,000 per Extension, approx. two (2) Extensions to be funded

IoT platforms that become Level 1 (L1) compliant need to integrate the symbloTe Interworking Interface with existing CLD components (it is assumed that IoT platforms have their backend hosted in the Cloud). This enables semantic interoperability and uniform access to IoT resources which a platform chooses to register and make discoverable via the symbloTe Core Services. The access to those resources stays under the control of a platform provider.

APP is designed to offer a unified view on different platforms to a new generation of cross-platform IoT applications. This is achieved by the symbloTe Core Services that can search for registered IoT resources across platforms. Note that the Core Services store and

manage only IoT resource descriptions (i.e. resource metadata), while the access to those resources (e.g., sensor data and actuation) is provided by the underlying platforms. Thus, the symbloTe Core Services are in close interaction and collaboration with the services provided within the Cloud Domain which offer the actual access to virtualized IoT resources. In addition to the search functionality, the Core Services implement symbloTe specific authentication and authorization mechanisms providing the means for secure access to underlying platform-specific resources.

Figure 7: Illustrating Level 1 Compliance

Figure 7 shows the benefits of L1 compliance by an example depicting two platforms A and B using the symbloTe Core Services. When an application searches for devices and identifies adequate ones, the application accesses the devices offered by the two platforms through the Interworking Interface. In other words, cross-platform applications i) use the symbloTe Core Services to find adequate devices across platforms and ii) access, integrate and use those devices through an uniform and open interface. We are supporting a part of the OData standard for pull-based access to platform devices and provide a push-style mechanism for continuous delivery of sensor data to applications over WebSockets.

symbloTe Information Model. To reach the goal of semantic interoperability, i.e., “the ability of computer systems to exchange data with unambiguous, shared meaning”, symbloTe defines three types of Information Models related to the description of resources which platforms want to expose through symbloTe:

- The **Core Information Model (CIM)** defines all information that symbloTe needs to understand on an abstract level, e.g. a class *Sensor* that is related to the class *Location* via a relation/property *hasLocation*.
- **Platform-Specific Information Models (PIMs)** are platform-specific and contain all classes and their relations which a platform wants to expose through symbloTe, e.g., a custom property of a *Sensor* called *hasColor*. A PIM is an extension of the CIM and must comply to it, e.g., by creating new sub-classes that are based on definitions from CIM.
- The **Best Practice Information Model (BIM)** is a special form of a PIM that is predefined by and shipped with symbloTe. Its purpose is to provide a default and

simplified way to use symbloTe whenever a platform does not require having a custom PIM.

When exposing IoT devices to symbloTe Core Services, devices need to be semantically described. This can be done using one of the following two approaches:

- Using the BIM: As the BIM is a complete information model and known to symbloTe you will be able to register devices via a simple REST-based call with JSON payload.
- Using a custom PIM: If the BIM does not fit your needs, you can describe the exposed resources of your platform using a custom PIM which must be compliant to the CIM. This must be expressed as an ontology using the Resource Description Format (RDF)². The symbloTe team can provide support for this task.

symbloTe components for L1 compliance. symbloTe Core Services are composed of APP components, which enable the interaction between third-party applications and platforms. The main services of the Core are the following:

1. *Administration* – provides a web-based GUI as well as an API for platform administrators. The provided functionality includes: creation and management of the platform and its properties, generation of platform credentials for authentication.
2. *Registry* – repository for storing all platform-related metadata. It provides an API for registering and updating of platforms and their resources. During the registration process, unique resources' IDs are generated.
3. *Search Engine* – enables applications to find relevant registered devices/services within the Registry. Stores the required information in RDF store.
4. *Semantic Manager* – utility component for validating RDF descriptions used to describe PIM and resources. Also provides translation mechanism between RDF and Java objects.
5. *Resource Monitor* – tracks the availability of registered devices in order to ensure their availability.
6. *Resource Access Monitor* – provides access links to the resources and tracks information about resource popularity.
7. *Core Authentication and Authorization Manager* – authenticates third-party users and applications (i.e., users and applications that are not associated with any IoT platform) and provides credentials required to access symbloTe Services. It also supports trust relationships between platforms, as it acts as the root certification authority.
8. *Anomaly Detection Module* – is responsible for detecting 0-day attacks and other types of security violations (malicious users, DoS attacks) by using a signature-less machine-learning approach.

The Core Services are designed and implemented based on the microservices architecture (using Spring Cloud), having in mind the scalability and distributed characteristics of the architecture. The listed services will be offered and managed by the symbloTe consortium. The ones which are of particular interest to platforms are the

² <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

Administration Service, Registry and Resource Monitor, since they are accepting requests from symbloTe-enabled platforms.

The following CLD components will facilitate the integration of a new platform with symbloTe. All interfaces mentioned here are part of the Interworking Interface, which exposes platform devices as IoT services. The symbloTe consortium will provide interface definitions for all components (REST and messaging system based on Rabbit AMQP) together with a supporting Java library implementing non-platform-specific parts of those components.

1. *Registration Handler* – handles platform-side registration of devices with the Registry by using the symbloTe Information Model. An interface description will be provided along symbloTe implementation in Java, which needs configuration according to platform specifics.
2. *Resource Access Proxy* – enables secure access to the IoT resources offered by the IoT platform and registered within the Registry. A plug-in template and interface description will be provided which needs to be implemented by the platform owner so as to forward requests to platform-specific actions and return results (resource data). Implementation of the non-platform specific parts will be provided by the symbloTe consortium.
3. *Platform Authentication and Authorization Manager* – offers authentication and authorization mechanisms on the platform side. Authentication uses standardized Public Key Infrastructure approach whereas authorization is based on the Attribute-Based Access Control mechanism. The symbloTe consortium provides a Java implementation for this component.
4. *Monitoring component* – monitors the status of registered devices/services and reports the status periodically to the Resource Monitor within the Core Services.

The aforementioned components will need to be integrated by the applicants and platform-specific parts will need to be implemented to connect symbloTe Core Services with real platform resources. The symbloTe team will provide interface definitions and component implementations in Java that require further extensions to be integrated with platform-specific components and security schemes. We acknowledge the fact that all extensions written in other languages require more resources.

To make a platform Level 1 compliant, applicants need to do the following:

- Analyze the symbloTe solution for Level 1 compliance
- Expose the description IoT devices accessible through symbloTe either using the symbloTe BIM or a custom PIM (in the form of an ontology).
- Integrate the Interworking Interface required for Level 1 compliance within the CLD domain with their platforms
- Provide feedback and comments which can improve and simplify the process of creating L1 platforms

What will symbloTe offer to applicants to make their platforms L1 compliant?

- A documented design and prototype implementation of the required symbloTe Core Services

- A documented Interworking Interface and corresponding components in Java for CLD
- An example procedure for mapping of an existing information model to the symbloTe information model
- A documented example explaining the process for creating a L1 platform based on the example of the open-source OpenIoT platform

Related Use Cases, Trials and IoT platforms. L1 supports the following symbloTe use cases and trials:

- i) *Smart Mobility and Ecological Urban Routing*, planned in the cities of Zagreb, Vienna and Porto, with 3 IoT platforms involved up to now, offering air quality, noise level and mobility/traffic/parking related data,
- ii) *Smart Residence*, planned in Pisa, Vienna and Barcelona, with 3 IoT platforms involved up to now, offering data related to smart assisted living, indoor air quality as well as domotics, and
- iii) *Smart Stadium*, planned in Barcelona, with 2 IoT platforms involved up to now, offering beacons platform for indoor location and promowalls.

Additionally, from the 1st Open Call, the selected Third Parties contribute to the following use cases: Smart Building, Smart Marinas and Smart Cities.

4.3.2 symbloTe-OC2-L2

Topic Summary

Purpose: To make 3rd party IoT platforms L2-compliant, so that they join platform federations. Applicants should explicitly mention with which symbloTe platforms they would like to federate with (see list of available platforms at the end of this topic) and what could be the business value out of this federation. A desired feature would be that apart from making their IoT platform L2-compliant, they also extend their native apps to display/access/control federated resources.

Commitment: Applicants should make their platforms and their resources available during the symbloTe demos and trials (mid/end 2018).

Type of Applicants: IoT Platform owners / operators

Funding: up to €50,000 per Extension, approx. four (4) Extensions to be funded

symbloTe Level 2 (L2) compliance enables organizational interoperability focusing on inter-platform communication and collaboration. In contrast to L1 compliance, L2 compliance targets the efficient resource sharing and access between compliant IoT platforms by forming federations. Thus, within a federation, platforms can securely interoperate, collaborate and share resources, which should be described based on the Information Model defined in L1 allowing the introduction of smart semantic approaches in order to expose IoT devices, and according to the accepted Service Level Agreement (SLA) defined on federation level.

By targeting interoperability between platforms on CLD, connected native applications are able to leverage the benefits and increase their business value by consuming and

processing additional resources made available by other platforms and shared within the federation.

Based on the implemented bartering functionalities provided by the symbloTe reference implementation, additional resource and data distribution channels on platform side are feasible. Through bartering, a level of fairness between platforms can be achieved, guaranteeing that the amount of shared resources between platforms is balanced. Moreover, the introduction of trust calculation at different levels (resources and platform) ensures the accurate reliability and reputation information for the members of the federation, influencing on the Bartering functionalities.

Figure 8: Level 2 compliance

Figure 8 shows an example of resource access for a native application to its home platform inside a federation. In it, the platforms have their own registry of shared resources, which contains their own devices and some devices of other platforms in the federation in which they might be interested. In this scenario, the symbloTe core holds information about SLA agreements signed between the different platforms of the federation, some Bartering and Trading information as well as membership information and status. This information is propagated to the different participants in the federation as well.

When a native application of platform A searches for resources, it will receive resources from both, platform A and B since both are in the same federation and in this case, Platform A is interested in some resources of Platform B, which are valuable to the aforementioned application. As such, those resources are in its local registry so, when the application executes the search request, it will receive a list of available devices from both platforms. To make life easier to application developers, maintain to a minimum the work needed to adapt a native application and be able to work with symbloTe on a compliance Level 2, the IoT Platform Owner might provide a compatibility layer that will translate from the Common Information Model, spoken by the Interworking API, to the platform specific

information model before returning the data to the application. This layer can also talk to any other platform in the federation easily as the transformation of data will be the same for platform A and B since both of them provide it in the CIM. That way, the application will need just minimal modifications to adapt to the symbloTe security paradigm. It even might remain unchanged if the compatibility layer also takes care of the security paradigm transformation.

In this section, we highlight the components that an IoT platform needs to integrate with existing components in CLD in order to become L2 compliant, as well as the Core Service components mainly required for managing federations and reaching an agreement for a platform to join a federation. Since authenticated and authorized access to offered services is vital for an IoT ecosystem, we also include security-related components as outlined in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Core and Cloud Components applicable for Level 2 compliance

The Core Services are deployed on a central server and managed by the symbloTe project team. Therefore, the platforms just have to integrate and interact with the well documented interfaces. On the other side, to make an IoT platform fully L2 compliant, the listed CLD components have to be installed, deployed and run on each platform interacting with the native platform functionalities.

symbloTe Information Model. The Information models for the description of the exposed resources are the same that have been defined at L1 and the platforms should decide how to semantically describe their devices in the federation based on the two approaches introduced at L1. Therefore, the Information Model defined at L1 is valid for L2, however the main difference is that now the information is distributed among all the platforms and it is not centralized such as in L1.

symbloTe components for L2 compliance. The following Core Services components interact to provide the L2 functionality:

1. *Core Bartering* – comprises all bartering functionalities that need to be centralized and coordinated by the symbloTe Core Services. Especially the bartering features between federated platforms will be highlighted. These include validating issued

vouchers and reporting to the Trust Manager when a platform within a federation is not cooperating.

2. *Core Authentication and Authorization Manager* – may also participate in federations. Acting as the root certification authority it also has the power to revoke misbehaving platforms certificates and invalidate all credentials originating from them.
3. *Administration* – provides a web-based GUI for the management of federations. The provided functionality includes: creation and management of federations and their properties, management of security attributes used to access federated resources.
4. *SLA Engine* – manages the whole lifecycle of service level agreements (SLAs) for the federation (definition, negotiation, monitoring, etc).

The following CLD components will facilitate a new IoT platform becoming member of a federation. All interfaces mentioned here are part of the Interworking Interface, which exposes platform devices as IoT services. The symbloTe consortium will provide interface definitions for all components (REST and messaging system based on Rabbit AMQP) together with a supporting Java library implementing non-platform-specific parts of those components.

1. *Platform Registry* – maintains the actual state of shared (own and foreign) resources within the federation. It also enables a local search of relevant resources, which are offered by other platforms, in contrast to L1.
2. *Subscription Manager* – in contrast to L1, the subscription and notification of any changed resource status or properties are propagated in a distributed fashion between the federated platforms.
3. *Federation Manager* – is responsible for managing all required federation information needed on platform level, like federation and SLA updates, updates on access policies and trust levels.
4. *Optimization Manager* – supports the suggestion of equivalent resources offered within the federation to ensure optimized resource usage by taking power consumption and availability aspects into account.
5. *Trust Manager* – introduces a multi-layer trust calculation on resource and platform level, which may impact the usage and acceptance of platforms and their offered resources.
6. *Resource Access Proxy* – enables secure access to the IoT resources offered to the federation. A plug-in template and interface description will be provided which needs to be implemented by the platform owner so as to forward requests to platform-specific actions and return results (resource data). Implementation of the non-platform specific parts will be provided by the symbloTe consortium.
7. *Platform Authentication and Authorization Manager* – in addition to L1, supports the efficient and secure issuing of federated credentials used to access resources offered within the federation. Those credentials are then, in the federated platforms, validated against the existing federations definitions. The definitions (members and access policies) are provisioned into this module from the Federation Manager.

8. *Bartering and Trading Manager* – acts as the counterpart of the Core Services component, initializes and manages the voucher creation and assignment for each platform. It also interacts and communicates with the Core Bartering component for voucher consumption and validation.
9. *Monitoring* – collects and monitors the status and load of offered resources within the federation and also supports the transmission of aggregated metadata about the resource health to the SLA engine.

The aforementioned components will need to be integrated by the applicants and platform-specific parts will need to be implemented to connect symbloTe Core Services with real platform resources. The symbloTe team will provide interface definitions and component implementations in Java that require further extensions to be integrated with platform-specific components and security schemes. We acknowledge the fact that all extensions written in other languages require more resources.

To make a platform Level 2 compliant, applicants need to do the following:

- Analyse the existing symbloTe solution and reference implementation for Level 2 compliance
- Integrate, install, deploy and run the CLD components
- Integrate the Interworking interface required for Level 2 compliance within the CLD domain with the IoT platform
- Integrate the platform with the core services
- Create or join a federation and share their resources in the federation

To be able to improve our system, components and documentation continuously, we request all participants to provide feedback so we can enhance and simplify the process of creating L2 platforms.

What will symbloTe offer to applicants to make their platforms L2 compliant?

- A documented design and reference implementation of the required symbloTe Core Services
- The documented Interworking interface and corresponding components in Java for CLD
- An example procedure and documented example for setting up the federation L2 platform
- Core service components up and running for L2, in order to be used in the federation management

Adaptation of the native applications (optional).

Applicants could also adapt their existing native applications in order to use the resources of the federated platforms through the symbloTe mechanisms.

Therefore, the applicants who want to integrate and evolve their native applications need to do the following:

- Make their platforms L2 compliant.

- Integrate and evolve their native applications to be L2 compliant – symbloTe offers reference Java client libraries as well as standardized REST APIs.
- Participate in a federation and verify access to resources from other members through the symbloTe APIs in the symbloTe extended native applications.

To be able to improve the usability of L2 compliance, we request all participants to provide feedback so we can enhance and simplify the usage of the federation features.

What will symbloTe offer to applicants to integrate their native applications at L2 compliant?

- A documented design and reference examples to integrate it with L2
- An example procedure and documented example for using the federation L2 platform.

Related Use Cases, Trials and IoT platforms. L2 supports the following symbloTe use cases and trials:

- EduCampus*, planned in the city of Karlsruhe, involving indoor positioning and room reservation systems
- Smart Mobility and Ecological Urban Routing*, planned in the cities of Zagreb and Vienna, with 2 IoT platforms involved up to now, offering air quality and noise level data.
- Smart Residence*, planned in Pisa and Barcelona, with 2 IoT platforms involved up to now, offering data related to indoor air quality as well as domotics.

Applicants need to decide which of the existing IoT platforms they want to federate with so as to enhance or extend the aforementioned use cases.

4.3.3 symbloTe-OC2-L3/4

Topic Summary

Purpose: To make 3rd party IoT gateways and/or IP native families of devices L3/4-compliant. The proposed Extensions must include at least 10 devices of at least 3 different types. Such devices can be: i) gateway-controlled devices, ii) IP-native smart devices or iii) a mix of the previous.

Commitment: Applicants must join a challenge event (end 2018) to demonstrate their solution and to pass a set of symbloTe-defined interoperability tests.

Type of Applicants: IoT Gateway and/or IP native device manufacturers, system integrators

Funding: up to €40,000 per Extension, approx. four (4) Extensions to be funded

In L3/4 compliance, interoperability is considered at the gateway/smart device level. Devices and gateways can directly expose their resources to interested consumers (other devices, gateways or applications) in proximity. *Smart Space (SSP)* Domain provides services for discovery and registration of new IoT devices in dynamic local smart spaces, dynamic configuration of devices in accordance with predefined policies in those environments, and well-documented interfaces for devices available in smart spaces. *Smart Device (SDEV)* Domain relates to smart devices and their roaming capabilities. We assume that devices have the capabilities to blend with a surrounding smart space while they are on the move. In other words, smart devices can interact with devices in a visited smart space, which are managed by a visited platform, in accordance with predefined access policies. To achieve these points, the symbloTe projects defines a SSP/SDEV infrastructure. An high level overview of a SSP is presented in the following figure.

Figure 10 Level 2/3 Compliance

The idea is the following: an SSP is defined from a set of software modules that reside in a local gateway. The symbloTe-enabled devices (sensors and actuators) could exist as a standalone device, communicating directly with the local gateway, or could be part of a local platform; in both cases, they will have to deploy an agent in order to communicate with the SSP. Moreover, any application running on a smartphone that wants to use the local resources should talk with the SSP using the interfaces provided. In order for a device to become symbloTe-enabled it needs to develop a layer - the *symbloTe agent* - that interacts with the SSP based on a well-defined communication protocol. This is all that a device/local platform manufacturer should develop to interact with the symbiote ecosystem at SSP level.

symbloTe Information Model. In the smart space architecture, gateways and devices have their own symbloTe agent component that lets them interact with the rest of the symbloTe Smart Space ecosystem. The representation of the exchanged information is based on CIM introduced by symbloTe (see L1 for more details).

symbloTe components for L3/4 compliance. The following components interact to provide the L3/4 functionality:

1. *Innkeeper* – represents the point of entry for gateways and devices to the SmartSpace. This component is also tasked to communicate with the Resource Access Point component to keep the resources URIs consistent.
2. *Resource Access Proxy* – acts as connection between the symbloTe ecosystem and devices/gateway, receiving requests from the symbloTe's upper layers and adapting them to be processed by the devices/gateways symbloTe agent.
3. *Local Authentication and Authorization Manager* – provides local security management system. Its main purpose is to interface directly the symbloTe's upper layer security infrastructure, and provide a local interface to it. This mechanism allows the smart space to operate in some restricted fashion if local connectivity is not available, and therefore core security mechanisms are also unavailable.
4. *symbloTe agent* – is the interface between devices and symbloTe ecosystem. This agent can run on platform gateways or directly in devices; depending on where the agent runs, it could provide different API.

These components provide a set of services to interact with the local SSP: leaving out the registration/update process, an application or a symbloTe agent can request the list of the available resources and get/send data to them.

To make a platform L3/4 compliant, applicants need to do the following:

- Analyze the existing symbloTe solution and reference implementation for Level 3/4 compliance.
- Integrate, install, deploy and run the SSP components.
- Develop the symbloTe agent for their gateways/devices.
- Participate in the challenge event where their gateways/devices will pass some test to validate their L3/4 compliance.

What will symbloTe offer to applicants to make their platforms L3/4 compliant?

- symbloTe provides documentation about the implemented interfaces between the agent and the modules inside the SSP, including also the semantic description that should adopt the resources;
- symbloTe provides the software modules to create a local instance of SSP gateway with the symbloTe middleware. This gateway can be hosted on common x86-based machine.

4.3.4 symbloTe-OC2-Apps

Topic Summary

Purpose: To build a smart phone application (Android or iOS) that combines resources offered by L1-compliant platforms and/or available Domain Enablers and demonstrates cross-domain features. Proposed applications should focus in the domains of Smart City, Smart Residence and Smart Stadium/Buildings, as well as combination of the above.

Commitment: Applicants should make their applications available for a demo during the symbloTe trials (mid/end 2018).

Type of Applicants: Mobile app companies

Funding: up to €20,000 per Extension, approx. three (3) Extensions to be funded

One of the key goals of symbloTe is to demonstrate the easiness of developing IoT applications over the defined uniform and secure interface of L1-compliant platforms, as well as utilizing the advance intelligence and analytics capabilities of available Domain Enablers. In this topic, we look for Extensions that will build new IoT applications or will extend existing IoT applications so as to utilize the symbloTe Core Services and be able to access the resources offered by the L1-compliant platforms. For more info on L1 compliance, please refer to the *symbloTe-OC2-L1* topic. In addition, certain Domain Enablers that collect, aggregate and process data from various L1-compliant platforms can be utilized.

Available L1-compliant platforms. Below a list of the currently available L1-complaint platforms is provided. The list is expected to grow and include the beneficiaries from the 1st Open Call.

- Open IoT Platform: OpenIoT is an open-source Cloud platform for the Internet of Things. It manages the registration, data acquisition and deployment of different sensors using the Semantic Web technologies and the SSN ontology, thus enabling the semantic unification of diverse data and IoT applications in the Cloud. In symbloTe, OpenIoT realizes a Mobile Crowdsensing Air Quality Platform offering support for discovering and collecting data in a crowdsensing fashion from wearable sensors through a Cloud-based Publish/Subscribe Middleware. Such a platform can be used for applications related to air quality monitoring and services, for which the users' wearables will provide air quality measurements. The crowd sensing air quality service operates on the data gathered through OpenIoT.
 - Offered data: Mobile sensors that measure air quality information (CO, NO2), temperature, humidity, pressure. Mobile phones provide noise and luminosity data.

- openUWEDAT: The cities of Zagreb and Vienna operate Air Quality Measurement Networks, whose data is typically collected from fixed stations using the platform called “Stationary Air Quality Platform” (openUWEDAT). This way, mobile data collected via OpenIoT platform can be complemented by data provided by openUWEDAT for improving the accuracy by minimizing measurement errors related to data from mobile sensors.
 - Offered data: Mainly urban area air quality data originating from stationary, high-accuracy measuring stations.
- MoBaaS Platform: The Mobility Backend as a Service (MoBaaS) offers a set of services, in the form of APIs, which intend to eliminate the friction created by having services from multiple vendors. This includes the integration of data from many sources, focusing on the mobility aspect of the city. In symbloTe, MoBaaS is foreseen for the applications including the routing service based on preferences such as points of interest, air quality, distances, and amount of traffic and parking availability.
 - Offered data: Mainly mobility data such as POIs, spatial air quality, distances, traffic conditions, parking availability.
- Symphony Platform: Symphony is an IoT platform used for the integration of home/building control functionalities, devices and heterogeneous subsystems. Symphony can monitor, supervise and control many different building systems, devices, controllers and networks available from third-party suppliers. By intelligently correlating cross-system information, a flexible and highly efficient platform is delivered to the stakeholders. The system is a service-oriented middleware integrating several functional subsystems into a unified IP-based platform. As hardware/software compound, Symphony encompasses media archival and distribution, voice/video communications, home/building automation and management, and energy management.
 - Offered data: Sensors and actuators such as lights, dimmers, RGB lights, curtains.
- KIOLA Platform: KIOLA is an IoT telehealth platform. It is able to store health and person-related data, and register sensor information of personal health devices (e.g. body weight, blood pressure). Additionally, users can be identified using Bluetooth beacons (BLE). An additional plugin serves as a wrapper for commercially available fitness trackers. Using the plugin fitness trackers such as Fitbit or Nokia Health can also be registered with the symbloTe core.
 - Offered data: Mainly health and person-related data, including activity tracker, body weights, blood pressure, as well as information on Bluetooth beacons and fitness trackers.
- nAssist Platform: The IoT platform is a software platform designed and conceived to allow agile, continuous management of data in the energy efficiency, security and automation fields. It is built following a Service Oriented Architecture paradigm and has been designed to be easily adapted to different areas of application that use, or implicitly need, data collection and data processing from logical or physical devices (sensors and actuators). One application of nAssist is that of monitoring and controlling a number of direct parameters related to indoor air quality, such as CO2 levels, humidity and temperature. In addition, this platform monitors and

controls other factors that are important for indoor environmental quality considerations such as light and noise, as they also affect occupants.

- Offered data: Mainly indoor air quality, humidity and temperature, and luminosity levels data.
- Beacons Platform / Visitor Platform / PromoWall Platform / Retailer Platform: These platforms are part of the smart stadium use case and represent the underlying IoT environments (beacons, visitor information, promo-wall control, and retailer platform). Visitors in the stadium, using the visitor app in their smart phone and the indoor location beacons, find and access nearby services provided by Retailers (shops and moving carts) through the retailer app in their tablets and the indoor location services. Retailers find Promowall devices and send info & promotions to them.
 - Offered data: Apps in each device (mobile, tablet, PromoWall, etc.) act as sensors (location) and actuators for the associated actions (show promotion, place order, etc.). The data interchanged is the beacon map, the devices (visitor, retailer) availability & location, the retailer offerings, the purchasing orders and the info & promotions for the Promowalls.
- Navigo Digitale Platform: The Navigo Digitale IoT Platform is a platform created to manage digital assets pertaining to harbors used for boating and yachting. Its scope embraces both physical entities (objects) and immaterial entities (documents and workflows). It consists of a distributed platform, with instances associated to different ports across Europe and running part in the cloud, and part on premise. The ultimate purpose of ND is to provide services to the harbor's activities (B2B) and to its end-users (B2C). An interface to Navigo's PortNet application provides access to the harbors control application.
 - Data: Mainly data on mooring process and parameters (location, distance, time, speed, water tanks levels, arrival time, latest routes, fuel situation, emissions, environmental sensor data, etc.).

Available Domain Enablers. Domain Enablers are virtual IoT platforms which combine data from different IoT platforms and provide this data either as is (raw data), or in an aggregated or processed manner. They can be accessed using L1 interfaces. Below, we describe the currently available Domain Enablers by symbloTe.

- Green Route Enabler obtains air quality data from the platforms and interpolates the data with the street segments of the map being used in order to obtain the air quality of a given street. These data are provided to the routing services (either the ones residing within a platform or external services), which, combining with other data, such as traffic or parking, are able to compute green routes. Additionally, the data provided by the platforms can also be used to obtain POIs of interest to the users.

To make a symbloTe-powered smart phone application, applicants need to do the following:

- Analyse the symbloTe solution for Level 1 compliance
- Build or extend a smart phone application that uses resources offered by L1-compliant platforms and/or available Domain Enablers

- Provide feedback and comments which can improve and simplify the process of creating L1-compliant applications

What will symbloTe offer to applicants to built symbloTe-powered applications?

- A documented design and API of the symbloTe Core Services and Domain Enablers
- A deployed instance of Core Services, with the metadata of the available L1-compliant platforms
- A deployed instance of Domain enablers, with the processed domain-specific data
- A documentation of the used information model
- Description of available IoT platforms that are symbloTe enabled, and description of planned trials

4.3.5 symbloTe-OC2-Trials

Topic Summary

Purpose: To involve end users and citizens that will use our applications and hardware (portable sensors, etc) to support our "Smart Mobility and Ecological Urban Routing" trial.

Commitment: Support the trials planned in Zagreb, Vienna and Porto (mid/end 2018).

Type of Applicants: NGOs, municipalities, organizations, companies with end users in Zagreb, Vienna and Porto.

Funding: up to €15,000 per Extension, approx. three (3) Extensions to be funded

The symbloTe project has planned a number of trials in various locations. The purpose of the Extension is to strengthen the planned Smart City related trials in Vienna, Zagreb and Porto. More specifically, the **Smart Mobility and Ecological Urban Routing** use case involves the collection of air quality information from not only stationary sensing stations but also mobile wearable sensors, which is processed to obtain the air quality index for the various streets of the city. This information can later be used, through applications, to calculate the ecological routes to the users' destinations or to support the search for points of interest (POI) within the city.

As such, the expectation from the trials of this use case is for an end-user community to use the wearables during their daily commute, providing air quality data of the locations they visit. Additionally, users are also expected to use the applications developed within the Use Case to obtain the ecological routes (which are influenced by the data they provided) and to search for POIs. These trials are directed at NGOs (green/cyclists organizations) and municipalities of Vienna, Zagreb and Porto.

The Extensions must include the number of participants, the location of the trials as well as the necessary budget for trial implementation (which has to take into account the cost of wearables for air quality monitoring). Note that a smaller number of participants is need to perform air quality monitoring using wearables, while a larger community of users can use applications developed by the symbloTe consortium for ecological routing and POI search. Thus, the number of trial participants is by no means limited by the number of

available wearables. In addition, the participating organization needs to consider costs for the dissemination and promotion of their specific activity, in order to attract and incentivize an increased user community to participate in the organized trials.

The consortium will support the Extension to organize adequate air quality monitoring campaigns and lend whenever and if possible the wearables available among consortium partners for particular trials in order to optimize the usage of available wearables. The planning of the trials should be performed within the first month of the Extension.

Technical details for the wearables: The wearables for air quality monitoring should be reasonably small and portable, with autonomy of operation for at least one day. They should include a Bluetooth module for communication with a smartphone and use an open protocol for transmitting sensor readings directly to the smartphone. They should include at least one of the following sensors for gases: carbon monoxide, nitrogen dioxide, particulate matter or volatile organic compounds (VOCs). The price range of such devices is €200 to €450 per unit.

5 Applicant’s Guide

In this section, we include the material provided to the applicants so as to help them with the discovery of the available material and information, as well as to make them familiar with the F6S platform, which is used for the submission of the Open Call proposals.

5.1 symbloTe site walkthrough

Below we provide a quick walkthrough of the symbloTe web site, so that the applicants can easily find the necessary information for our 2nd Open Call.

5.1.1 Finding the 2nd Open Call web page

The web page hosting all the information and material for the 2nd Open Call is available via the top menu of the [symbloTe web site](#), by selecting the option “2nd Open Call” under the “Open Calls” menu option, as shown in the screenshot below.

5.1.2 Available information and material

Once you go to the “2nd Open Call” page, the following tabs are available: “Call Information”, “Call Material”, “Important Dates”, “Feasibility Check” and “FAQ”, as shown in the following screenshot.

Call Information includes all the basic information about the call, i.e., the submission deadline, the expected duration of the Extensions (i.e., the funded proposals) the budget dedicated for this open call and the maximum budget per Extension, as well as the type of activities envisioned and the type of applicants expected. Finally, and perhaps most importantly, it includes the links for the **help-desk service**, i.e. a simple e-mail based service where you can ask questions (that may not be covered by the “FAQ” section) on Management or Technical issues, as well as the link to the **submission platform**, i.e. the **F6S platform**.

Help-desk	Management Issues		Technical Issues	
Proposal Submission Platform	symbloTe-OC2-L1 - L2 - L3/4:		Apply Now	
	symbloTe-OC2-Apps:		Apply Now	
	symbloTe-OC2-Trials:		Apply Now	

Call Material includes all the documents that are necessary for the applicants to understand the details of the call (summary and technical details), this guide for applicants, the eligibility and evaluation criteria, the template for the list of deliverables required in the application form, as well as a template for the Standard Extension Contract, to be signed by the symbloTe coordinator and the accepted Third Parties for the implementation of their Extensions.

Important Dates include all the dates related to this Open Call that applicants should take notice of.

The **Feasibility Check** includes a form for applicants to submit an early summary of their intended proposal to the symbloTe consortium. The team will evaluate your summary and come back within 10 days from your submission, with high-level comments, mainly on the eligibility of your proposal, and what aspects you need to strengthen. This service can be used only once per proposal. All fields are required and the summary should be in pdf format, not more than two (2) pages. If the summary exceeds the 2 pages, the exceeding ones will be ignored.

Your Name (required)

Your Email (required)

Title of proposal (required)

Proposal Topic (required)

symbloTe-OC2-L1
 symbloTe-OC2-L2
 symbloTe-OC2-L3/4
 symbloTe-OC2-Apps
 symbloTe-OC2-Trials

Upload your proposal (required; 2 pages max; pdf expected)

No file chosen

I'm not a robot

reCAPTCHA
Privacy - Terms

Finally, the **FAQ**, or “Frequently Asked Questions”, includes a number of questions and answers to clarify certain details of the Call. Please note that this section will be continuously updated with new material while the Call is still open, based also on the feedback received through the help-desk service.

Note: in order to get notified for any new material or updates for this Open Call, please subscribe to our **Notification Service**, simply by entering your name and e-mail to the respective form on the sidebar, above the countdown for the submission deadline, as shown below.

Open Call Notification Service

Name

Email *

2nd Open Call Submission Deadline

6	5	0	3	1	4	4	1
Days	Hours	Minutes	Seconds				

5.2 F6S submission platform walkthrough

For the submission of the proposals, we have selected the F6S platform, a well-established tool used by Investors and Accelerators to fund innovative projects. Since some of you may not be familiar with the specific platform, we provide here a short guide to help you with the submission process.

The symbloTe project has defined five (5) different topics for this 2nd Open Call, which are grouped into three (3) categories:

- **symbloTe Open Call 2: Platforms**, for topics symbloTe-OC2-L1, -L2 and L/34
- **symbloTe Open Call 2: Applications**, for topic symbloTe-OC2-Apps
- **symbloTe Open Call 2: Trials**, for topic symbloTe-OC2-Trials

By clicking on the respective “Apply Now” button on our website, you will be redirected to the respective F6S submission page and a welcome screen will pop up:

To join, you can select one of the three available options: **Facebook, LinkedIn or e-mail**. If you select one of the first two options, a pop-up will appear in order to grant F6S the permission to authenticate you through the selected platform. If you select to join via e-mail then you need to create a password and also fill in your first and last name.

It is possible to switch between different topics through the F6S navigation, by selecting the topic of your interest in the F6S’ symbloTe heading:

Once you connect to F6S, the application form will open.

Although you are now able to start filling-in the application form, we advise you to spend some time to **describe your team**.

Note that in our open call we allow only for single applicants, meaning single legal entities, i.e. companies, research groups, etc. However, it is highly advisable that you present us the team (or at least 2-3 key people) that will be working in the implementation of your

proposal, once accepted. To do so, you need to click the “Create Team” button in the “Let’s get started” section. If it is just you, then you can click on the respective button, but we do hope that the proposal will involve more than one person getting involved.

Once you click the “**Create Team**” button, you are then instructed to provide a number of details, like the Start-up/Team’s name and the team members (you can add people by providing their e-mail address or their name in case they already have an F6S account; if you want you can skip adding new team members and edit the entire team afterwards as well).

Afterwards, a short form for “**Basic Information**” needs to be filled in with the details of your team/start-up. This information will be valuable for the evaluators to judge the expertise and competencies of your team. So, the more details, the better 😊 If you join F6S using Facebook or LinkedIn some of this information may already be available, but you can change it.

Apart from defining the team members, it's important that each team member logs into F6S and update his/her profile with the skills, a short bio, past experience, etc. You can access your profile page by clicking on the profile icon in the upper right corner of F6S web site, as shown in the following screenshot (marked in red cycle).

Once you finish with the details of your team, then you can continue with the Open Call application form. Note that everything that is provided in F6S is **automatically saved**, i.e., you can always come back later (after joining in with the same credentials) and continue filling in the application form, from the point it you left it the last time. You can make as many edits or changes you like, until you submit the application. After the submission of the application, no changes are possible, apart from the ones related to the team description and your profile.

We will go briefly through the different application forms by underlining the main characteristics of each one: “Platforms”, “Applications” and “Trials”.

symbloTe Open Call 2: Platforms

The application form dedicated to Platforms providers. First, you shall include the title of your proposal and tick the topic you aim at applying. The submission form for platforms provider is actually identical for the following topics:

- symbiote-OC2-L1
- symbiote-OC2-L2
- symbiote-OC2-L3/4

Questions

Auto-Save Functionality

The below application form supports "auto-save" which works as follows: once you open and edit the form, your changes are automatically saved. You can then close the form and come back at any given moment (using the same F6S credentials) to continue editing your inputs. You can make as many changes you want up to the point where you submit your application. No changes are possible after the form submission.

1 **Proposal title ***

Please provide a simple and brief title for your proposal. Hint: you can use your IoT platform's name as the title of your proposal!

2 **Open call identifier ***

Please select the Open Call categories that your Extension applies to.

symbloTe-OC2-L1
 symbloTe-OC2-L2
 symbloTe-OC2-L3/4

The application then is divided in 6 categories: a) Basic Info, b) IoT solution, c) Innovation and Impact, d) Implementation, e) Data Management and f) Miscellaneous. In “**Basic Info**”, we expect information related to your company/organisation, the contact details of the main responsible whom we can get in touch to, if the proposal will be positively evaluated and, very important, a brief description of the team behind the extension, including the expertise that your organisation will deploy. Finally, a brief summary of your intended proposal will be the last item of this section.

A. Basic Info

3 **Affiliation type ***
Please select the type of your affiliation.

Start up SME Industry
 University Research Organisation Other

4 **Affiliation's legal name ***

5 **Country ***

6 **Main contact's full name ***

7 **Main contact's position in the affiliation ***

8 **Main contact's e-mail address ***

9 **Team description ***
Please provide a brief description of your team and expertise of the people involved in the Extension.

10 **Extension summary ***
Please provide a complete and coherent description of your Extension. Note: this info may be used by symbloTe for public reports and deliverables.

In “**IoT Solution**”, we expect some information about your IoT platform. More specifically, you need to provide a brief description, the business domains in which the platform is used, your clients and existing partnerships, your business vision with respect to interoperability (i.e., why interoperability is important for product) and finally a description of the technical details of your platform. For this last item, you need to provide a high-level technical description accompanied with a 2-page document (in pdf format) which can also include some more details along with some diagrams, which may ease the understanding of your solution.

B. IoT solution

11 Description of your IoT solution *
Please provide a brief, high-level description of your IoT solution

2000

12 Business domain(s) *
Please let us know in which business domain(s) your IoT solution applies to.

Smart Residence/Office Smart Campus Smart Mobility
 Smart Yachting Smart Stadium Smart City
 Other?

13 Clients and partnerships *
Please let us know who uses your solutions and in which context.

1500

14 Business vision *
Please let us know what are your business goals with respect to creating an interoperable platform

1500

15 Technical description *
Please provide a high level technical description of your IoT solution

Notes:
- For symbloTe-OC2-L1 submissions: among other, please identify connection with symbloTe use cases/ trials
- For symbloTe-OC2-L2 submissions: among other, please specify which symbloTe platforms you want to federate with
- For symbloTe-OC2-L3/4 submissions: among other, please provide a description of the type of gateways and/or devices you support

3000

16 Complementary technical description (Max file size 30MB) (Max file size 30MB.) *
Please upload an additional document (up to 2 pages long) describing certain technical details of your IoT solution (architecture diagram, software and hardware technologies used). Not necessary to repeat previously stated information.

In **“Innovation and Impact”**, we expect you to describe what type of resources (primitive IoT resources, such as sensor readings, etc) or services (including processed sensor readings, aggregated data, etc) you can open to third-party applications through the symbloTe platform. Moreover, a description of the benefits you expect to gain by making your IoT platform symbloTe-compatible is required.

C. Innovation and Impact

17 What resources/services will you open to the symbloTe ecosystem? *
Please describe what resources (sensor, actuators) or services (combination of resources) of your IoT solution you plan to make available to symbloTe.

3000

18 What benefits do you expect from joining the symbloTe ecosystem *
Please describe how you envision that the aforementioned offerings could potentially aid your business plans.

3000

In **“Implementation”**, we expect you to provide the details of your project, i.e. its duration, the number of deliverables to be generated throughout the duration of the project, as well

as the requested budget (personnel and travel). For the deliverables, there exists a template that includes a table where all deliverables should be mentioned, i.e., their title along with their type (documentation and/or software) and their submission date (in number of months after the start of the project/Extension). Concerning the budget, a specification of the costs' breakdown is required: please consider accurately that we expect you to join two meetings with the symbloTe consortium.

D. Implementation

19 **Duration of project ***
Please let us know how much time (in months; up to 6) you need to implement this Extension.

20 **List of deliverables (Max file size 30MB) (Max file size 30MB.) ***
Please let us know how many reports (R) and/or versions of your software (SW) you will provide to symbloTe and when. Please use the template provided (www.symbloTe-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/List-of-Deliverables-template.docx) and upload your plans (.pdf). Please consider that at the midterm and at the end of your extension you have to provide the "Technical Report" including all relevant information in order to enable the scheduled payment of the grant. The Technical Report Template is available as an annex of the symbloTe Standard Extension Contract (www.symbloTe-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/symbloTe-Standard-Extension-Contract.pdf).

CHOOSE A FILE

21 **Budget ***
Please let us know what budget you need to implement your Extension. Budget should cover your personnel and travel costs, including any overheads, if applicable. Regarding the travel costs, please consider that you will be invited to attend two one-day meetings with the symbloTe consortium in the duration of your Extension. Hence, make sure to allocate enough budget for this (consider an average cost for travelling in Europe about 600-800 euros per person).

€ ▾

22 **Budget break-down ***
Please provide the break-down of the requested budget: personnel costs, travel costs, overheads (if applicable).

In “Data Management”, we expect you to describe if and how you (plan to) deal with the collection, processing and storage of sensitive and/or private data, since this may render the interaction between symbloTe and with your platform not feasible.

E. Data Management

Does your IoT platform deal with sensitive and/or private end user data?

European Legislation foresees special protection for sensitive data of end users. More information is available here:

Personal data and privacy issue: For more information (link: eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/)
Sensitive Data assessment: See Section 4 (link: ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/doc/call/h2020/h2020-msca-itn-2015/1620147-h2020-guidance_ethics_self_assess_en.pdf)

23 **Does your IoT platform deal with sensitive and/or private end user data? ***
European Legislation foresees special protection for sensitive data of end users. More information is available here:
- Personal data and privacy issue: For more information (link: eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/)
- Sensitive Data assessment: See Section 4 (link: ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/doc/call/h2020/h2020-msca-itn-2015/1620147-h2020-guidance_ethics_self_assess_en.pdf)
Does your solution collect / store / use such sensitive data?

Yes
 No

24 **If YES, then do you comply with the respective EU legislation on the processing and storage of such data?**

How do you plan to modify your data management system in order to comply with EU regulation before the starting date of your project within symbloTe?

3000

Finally, in “Miscellaneous”, we would like to know how you did find out about our Open Call and agree with our privacy statement. As mentioned before, changes are possible at

any time before the deadline. Once you click on the “Submit Final” button, no further changes are possible.

F. Miscellaneous

25 **How did you find about our Open Call? ***
Please let us know through which channels you discovered our Open Call. You can select more than one options.

symbloTe info channel (online, offline, in person)
 IoT-EPI info channel (online, offline, in person)
 EU info channel (online, offline, in person)

F6S info channel (newsletter)
 Other media (article, post)
 Personal network

26 **Privacy statement and use of your information ***
The symbloTe consortium will use the information received within Open Calls for statistical purposes and for platform optimizations and sustainability studies. The same information can also be used in an anonymous way to create reports required by the European Commission and for general communication activities. Specific information about technical solutions will be treated as confidential and will not be disclosed for commercial and business purpose, but solely for research aims.

I have read and understood this statement and agree with its contents.

Recommendations [?](#)

Ask for new Recommendations [?](#)

symbloTe Open Call 2: Applications

The submission form for “Application” is almost similar to “Platforms” form by having an introductory section including title and topic’ selection and then 6 categories as above described: a) Basic Info, b) IoT application, c) Innovation and Impact, d) Implementation, e) Data Management and f) Miscellaneous.

The main difference in this template from the previous one, concerns the **section C “Innovation and Impact”**. In this section, we added a third question concerning the future sustainability of the app after the end of the extension and description of your plans for increasing the users’ engagement.

C. Innovation and impact

17 **Which resources/services will you access from the ones offered by the symbloTe ecosystem? ***
Please describe which resources (sensor, actuators) or services (combination of resources) your IoT application needs access to. Please identify specific IoT platforms and/or Domain Enablers from the symbloTe ecosystem your application will interact with.

3000

18 **What benefits do you expect from joining the symbloTe ecosystem? ***
Please describe how you envision that the aforementioned offerings could potentially aid your business plans

3000

19 **Sustainability and user engagement ***
Please describe how you plan to increase the user engagement of your app (promotion, rewarding policies, etc.) after the end of the extension, its deployability in real life scenarios and the actions you plan to realize for ensuring its sustainability.

3000

symbloTe Open Call 2: Trials

The submission template related to Trials is very similar to the previous ones by having an introductory section including title and topic and then 6 categories as above described: a) Basic Info, b) Trial info, c) Innovation and Impact, d) Implementation, e) Data Management and f) Miscellaneous. We will describe here below the sections, which are specific of this Topic. For all the other sections, please refer to “Platform” submission template.

The **section A “Basic Info”** is similar to the main template as described in “Platforms” template but we added two different types of Applicants, which are eligible for this topic: NGOs and Municipalities/Local Authorities.

A. Basic Info

3 **Affiliation's type ***
Please select the type of your affiliation

NGO
 Municipalities / Local authorities
 SMEs / Organizations / Associations
 Other?

Section B “Trial Info” is tailored for getting specific information on trials. Applicants must, first select the city where their end user community will involved with our trials, then the following questions aims at describing the community and the experience of the applicants in this field.

B. Trial Info

11 **Involved city ***
Please identify which city trials you want to get involved in

Zagreb
 Vienna
 Porto

12 **Description of the end user community ***
Please describe the community/communities to be involved in the trials and why you think they are the right group to address these trials. Please describe the profiles of user groups you are planning to involve, including their number, roles, general mobility patterns (preferred transportation, local/regional/international, ...). Please describe your role in relation to the community/-ies, both formal and informal.

3000

13 **End-user engagement experience ***
Please describe your experience with end-user engagement, e.g. number of annual events/programmes, number of active participants, methodologies used, format of events, geographical scale. Please list your 3 best projects involving end-users, focusing on impact and results from end-user involvement, ideally in ICT context.

3000

14 **Complementary description (Max file size 30MB) (Max file size 30MB.) ***
Please upload an additional document (up to 2 pages long) - your community bylaws (if existing) and/or (anonymized/empty) declaration forms your community members sign.

Finally, **section C “Innovation and Impact”** is different from the previous templates because it is focused on the impact on the local communities, their engagement and the final output the trial will make available to symbloTe.

C. Innovation and impact

15 **What benefits do you expect from joining the symbloTe trials? ***
Please describe how you envision that your involvement in the trials could potentially affect the local community you are representing or your business/development plans, and how these trials fit into the wider activities of your organization.

3000

16 **Community engagement and promotion ***
Please describe the communication activities and promotion/rewarding actions you will put in place for increase the engagement and the growth of your community.

3000

17 **Results and feedback from the end-user community ***
Please describe what kind of feedback from the end-user community will you provide at the end of the Trials (e.g. air quality data, user experience feedback, etc)

3000

6 Additional Information on Application process

6.1.1 Deadline

The deadline for submitting a proposal for symbloTe's 2nd Open Call is the 31st of January 2018, at 17.00 CET (Brussels local time).

6.1.2 Eligible Applicants

The same eligibility criteria with the [H2020 rules of participation](#) (cf. Article 10) apply in this Open Call. More specifically, eligible to receive funding through this Open Call is any legal entity established in a Member State or associated country, or created under Union law. This Open Call focuses on attracting start-ups, SMEs, companies or research institutes/organizations, with legal entity established. Such entities can be IoT Platform owners/operators, IoT gateway manufacturers, IP native device manufacturers, system integrators, mobile app companies and NGOs, municipalities, and companies with end users in Zagreb, Vienna and Porto.

Legal entities established in the following countries are eligible to receive funding through this Open Call:

- The Member States (MS) of the European Union (EU), including their overseas departments (based on the [general H2020 rules](#))
- The EU Associated Countries participate in Horizon 2020 under the same conditions as EU Member States. There are, as of 7 November 2016, [sixteen countries associated to H2020](#).

Applications are for single parties only; no consortia are allowed.

Applicants can only be selected for funding for one proposal on the same call (even if the proposer submitted multiple proposals that are ranked high enough to be selected for funding, or if the proposer submitted multiple proposals in different topics)

6.1.3 Prepare and submit a proposal

All proposals must be submitted in English, through the online submission services on F6S platform, to become available at this link <https://www.f6s.com/opencall2symbiote> . More details are provided in Section 5.

6.1.4 Support services from symbloTe consortium

A set of on line supporting services are available for interested Applicants, as also described in Section 5:

- **Notification Service:** interested parties can subscribe to this service so that they can receive notifications and updates on the support material before and after the opening of the Open Call
- **Frequently asked questions (FAQ):** on-line documentation divided into technical and process questions and regularly updated during the Submission period of the Open Call

- **Helpdesk Service:** interested parties can ask questions to symbloTe consortium or even submit a summary of the intended proposal for pre-proposal feasibility check. The Helpdesk will be accessible through the e-mail opencall@symbiote-h2020.eu. The questions submitted should fall under one of the following categories:
 - Technical issues
 - Funding scheme and legal issues
 - Information and dissemination issues
 - Pre-proposal feasibility check.
- **Pre-proposal feasibility check Service:** The feasibility check is a support service offered by symbloTe consortium in order to check in advance and eventually support Applicants in better focusing their proposals on the scope of symbloTe. The feasibility check is available up to 20 days before the Open Call Submission deadline. Applicants who wish to make use of this support service must submit a short version of their proposal up to the 15th of December 2017 and can expect feedback to be provided no later than the 25th of December 2017.

6.2 *Funding conditions*

6.2.1 **Budget available**

symbloTe will make use of the mechanisms called "Cascade Funding" outlined for financial support of Third Parties (art. 15 GA). Third Parties will be finally supported for the implementation of selected Extension compliant with symbloTe scope and objectives.

The total amount of the second Open Call allocated for support to Third Parties is €540,000, which will be allocated to Selected Third Parties upon evaluation of proposals.

The participation of a Third Party and consequential award on the First Open Call does not impede the participation in the second Open Call.

The number of selected proposal will depend on the quality of the Extensions proposed and on the results of the Evaluation Process. The funding allocated for each selected Extension will amount up to a maximum budget that is defined per topic and with a funding rate of 100% of eligible costs.

6.2.2 **Eligible costs**

Eligible costs are those incurred during the implementation of the Extension and duly justified in the Reporting documents (Intermediate and Final reporting) by the Selected Third Party.

As indication, eligible costs are:

- a) Direct Costs: Personnel costs for the planned work
- b) Other Direct Costs: any direct costs different than Personnel, mainly covering Travel expenses and necessary equipment, if defined by the topic

- c) Indirect Costs: overhead costs of the Third Party calculated in the maximum percentage of 25% of the Total Direct Costs (a+b)

6.3 Duration of the commitment

Selected Extensions for funding will have a total expected duration of up to 6 months. Selected Extensions can start at the earliest on the 1st of April 2018. The deadline for the final report and documentation is expected no later than 6 months after the start of the extension and, in any case no later than the end of October 2018.

6.4 Agreement between Third Party and symbloTe Coordinator

The selected Third Parties will be linked to the symbloTe Consortium as "Third Party using Cascade Funding". Selected Third Parties will sign the symbloTe Standard Extension Contract with the symbloTe Coordinator. The **symbloTe Standard Extension Contract** is the main agreement establishing rights and obligations for Coordinator and Third Party. More details are given in Section 9.

7 Open Call Communication Activities

In order to promote the Open Call, to get the widest audience and to reach targeted applicants, a special dissemination campaign has been planned.

The reason to launch specific dissemination campaigns related to Open Calls lies in the opportunity to create awareness and interest in the community of IoT sector's companies and research centres potentially eligible for applications. symbloTe aims at awarding innovative SMEs, companies and research groups that can collaborate with the symbloTe consortium in order to provide extensions of the system. Communication and dissemination are the keys for stimulating involvement and attracting the most interesting applications.

The targeted applicants for symbloTe extension are companies, SMEs, start-ups and Research Groups, which are key players in the IoT domain and specifically: application developers, IoT platform providers, gateway manufacturers and Cloud operators.

The launch of the official announcement and related documentation happened at M22 (end of October 2017) for the second Open Call. From the publication of the official announcement to the deadlines, applicants will have a period of three (3) months for submitting their proposals. This time constraint requires at least a pre-announcement period in which potential applicants can acquire information and get more familiar with symbloTe focus and objectives.

The information campaigns performed during for the first Open Call has brought valuable results for the impact of the call itself and has demonstrated the effectiveness of the effort deployed. For the second Open Call the consortium will follow and will improve the communication activities by spreading pre-announcements, which actually will consist in the dissemination of high-level messages on expected proposal scopes, according to the different compliance levels required by symbloTe project for integration of Extensions.

According to the Open Call implementation plan, the information campaign will start at least one month before the launch of the official announcement and will be organized as follows:

1. Exploitation of all the existing communication channels already established and running as above described. In addition to press releases planned within the project, a specific section of the web site will be dedicated to Open Calls information and announcements;
2. Involvement of each symbloTe partner in disseminating pre-announcement information by deploying its own professional/scientific network. During the first Open Call a valuable number of contact (companies, associations, communities) has been collected and informed; such contact data base will be also exploited and improved for this second open call.
3. Exploitation of synergies established through the IoT-EPI Communication Work Group and Innovation Task Force for disseminating announcements on EU institutional web sites and networks.
4. Exploitation of the F6S symbloTe community created during the implementation of the first Open Call which consists in: nearly 268 individual connections and 78 teams.

The information campaigns and their key messages will be organized in strict synergy with work package "WP7 – Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardization".

A set of Information material will be created in order to disseminate Open Calls information both on line and “on site”, for example within international conferences and industrial brokerage events. The planned material is:

- A leaflet, which can be distributed on line and in paper copy.
- A short factsheet on the Open Call Objectives and funding scheme.
- Video recordings for the two webinars planned in order to attract more applicants and inform them on the scope of the call topics.

8 Evaluation procedures

Evaluation and ranking will be carried out by Panel consisting of two external evaluators selected by the symbloTe Consortium and approved by the European Commission Project Officer, as well as one third evaluator from the symbloTe consortium. The reason to include a third evaluator from within symbloTe, was due to the experience from the 1st Open Call, where some evaluators did not fully grasp the concept of symbloTe, hence their evaluation was not aligned with the symbloTe goals. The third evaluator will mainly have this role: to check how much inline is the submitted proposal with goals and vision of symbloTe.

For the external evaluators, a specific check will be carried out by the symbloTe Consortium partners in order to identify and avoid any Conflict of Interest and ensure the appropriate independence and transparency level of the whole procedure. All external experts will sign a Non-Disclosure Agreement (see APPENDIX B – Confidentiality and Conflict of Interest Declaration)

The external experts will be fully briefed on the ambition of the symbloTe project prior to the evaluation phase. A Briefing package will be provided to the Experts, which will be exactly the same as the material provided to the interested applicants.

8.1 Organization of remote evaluation meetings

The Evaluation sessions will be organised remotely with External and Independent Experts.

1. **Individual Reading and Assessment Phase:** Each proposal will be evaluated by three (3) Experts who will issue an Individual Assessment Report (IAR). The IAR will be sent to the symbloTe coordinator (or delegated person) prior to the consensus meeting. F6S platform allows to perform this evaluation phase through the platform. The IAR will be issued directly in the platform.
2. The **consensus meeting** will be realised remotely with the participation of all the Evaluators. Two symbloTe representatives will moderate the consensus meeting: the Project Coordinator and the Technical Manager. The symbloTe moderators will not be granted of voting power but will be appointed as Technical reference persons for Panellists' questions on compliance with symbloTe scope. A final score per proposal must be decided at the consensus meeting. The Moderators will take notes of the discussion and will assign one Rapporteur per proposal for the emission of the consolidated Evaluation Summary Report (ESR). An anonymous version of the ESR will be provided to each proposer upon completion of the evaluation process. After the Consensus Meeting each proposal will be assigned with a **Rank** and in the case of rejection with a proper **justification** for the Applicants.
3. **Ranking Phase:** members of the symbloTe consortium will carry out the final ranking of the proposals. This would usually be expected to follow the ranking resulting from the consensus of the external experts. However, and following EC guidelines, there may be objective reasons for objecting to a Third Party (for example for commercial competition reason) and so the next highest proposal may be selected. It may also be the case that the top ranked proposals overlap in

scope. If some special cases will occur, the decision taken by the Consortium will be fully documented to the EC Project Officer.

8.2 Timeline and duration of the evaluation process

The duration of the evaluation of the proposals and approval of evaluation results by the EU will be concluded within 1 month (30 calendar days) from the date of Submission deadline. In the case of this particular Call, the deadline for the notification of results to applicants is set to the 9th of March 2018.

All the Applicants will receive a feedback on their proposal in the form of the ESR (Evaluation Summary Report). The funded Application will be invited to negotiate and sign the Funding agreement by the symbloTe Project Coordinator.

8.3 Evaluation Criteria

The five different topics of the 2nd Open Call are grouped into 3 categories, as follows:

- symbloTe-OC2-L1, symbloTe-OC2-L2 and symbloTe-OC2-L3/4
- symbloTe-OC2-Apps
- symbloTe-OC2-Trials

Each category has its own submission form, as presented in Section 5.2; thus, each category has some topic-specific and some common criteria, as presented below:

- Section A: Basic Info [*Common*]
 - Team expertise: Please rate the expertise and profile of the team in relation to the proposed solution.
- Section B: IoT Solution [*symbloTe-OC2-L1, symbloTe-OC2-L2 and symbloTe-OC2-L3/4*]
 - Impact of IoT solution: Please rate how innovative is the described IoT solution with respect to the targeted business domains (markets), established clients and achieved partnerships.
 - Clarity of business vision and ambition: Please rate how clear and ambitious the business vision of the applicant is.
 - Maturity of the IoT solution involved and appropriateness of the approach: Please rate how mature the described IoT solution is from a technical perspective.
- Section B: IoT Application [*symbloTe-OC2-Apps*]
 - Impact of IoT application: Please rate how innovative is the described IoT application with respect to the targeted business domains (markets), established clients and achieved partnerships.
 - Clarity of business vision and ambition: Please rate how clear and ambitious the business vision of the applicant is.

- Potential of the IoT application involved and appropriateness of the approach: Please rate the potential and appropriateness of the described IoT application is from a technical perspective.
- Section B: Trial Info [*symbloTe-OC2-Trials*]
 - Appropriateness of the end-user community: Please rate how appropriate is the community described and the feasibility of the involvement plans.
 - Quality and engagement level of the end-user community: Please rate the level of vitality of the community and the representativeness of the end-user needs, as well as the applicant's experience with engaging such communities.
- Section C: Innovation and impact [*symbloTe-OC2-L1, symbloTe-OC2-L2 and symbloTe-OC2-L3/4*]
 - Clarity of the offered resources/services and alignment with symbloTe vision: Please rate how clearly the resources/services to be offered are described and how aligned these offerings are with the symbloTe vision
 - Extent of potential benefits from the involved IoT solution: Please rate how realistic and extensive are the envisioned benefits from joining the symbloTe ecosystem
- Section C: Innovation and impact [*symbloTe-OC2-Apps*]
 - Feasibility and alignment with symbloTe ecosystem: Please rate how feasible the resources/services to be accessed are within the symbloTe ecosystem
 - Extent of potential benefits from the involved IoT application: Please rate how realistic and extensive are the envisioned benefits from joining the symbloTe ecosystem.
 - Sustainability: Please rate the user engagement potential of the application and its sustainability and potential of deployment in real life.
- Section C: Innovation and impact [*symbloTe-OC2-Trials*]
 - Extent of potential benefits for the involved community: Please rate how realistic and extensive are the envisioned benefits from joining the symbloTe ecosystem.
 - Community engagement and feedback: Please rate the potential of end-user engagement and the sustainability of the community after the end of the extension, as well as the quality of the feedback expected.
- Section D: Implementation [*Common*]
 - Feasibility of work plan: Please rate how feasible is the work plan based on the requested duration, budget and timing of deliverables.
- Section E: Data Management [*symbloTe-OC2-L1, symbloTe-OC2-L2 and symbloTe-OC2-L3/4*]
 - Soundness of approach with respect to management of sensitive/private data, if applicable: Please rate how sound is the (planned) approach of the

described IoT solution to manage the involved sensitive/private data, in relation to the respective EU legislation.

- Section E: Data Management [*symbloTe-OC2-Apps*]
 - Soundness of approach with respect to management of sensitive/private data, if applicable: Please rate how sound is the (planned) approach of the described IoT application to manage the involved sensitive/private data, in relation to the respective EU legislation.

8.4 Criterion Scores

Each evaluation criteria will be assigned with 5 points (on F6S the number of “stars” will be increased at 10 in order to allow half points and reduce the incidence of equal scores). This choice has been taken in order to avoid further effort in interpreting different evaluation criteria and to perform an Evaluation process in line with EC standard procedures: both the potential proposers and evaluators are familiar with this format and so the process is streamlined. The overall score of the proposal is the sum of the score of each criterion.

Below the meaning of each score is provided:

- 0 - The proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be assessed due to missing or incomplete information
- 1 - POOR - The criterion is inadequately addressed, or there are serious inherent weaknesses
- 2 - FAIR - The proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses
- 3 - GOOD - The proposal addresses the criterion well, but a number of shortcomings are present
- 4 - VERY GOOD - The proposal addresses the criterion well, but a small number of shortcomings are present
- 5 - EXCELLENT - The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion

The only exception for the aforementioned scoring system is the last criterion about data management. Here, we use a qualitative scoring which is more appropriate, based from the experience of the 1st Open Call:

- Not applicable
- Not addressed
- Poorly addressed
- Well addressed

8.5 Threshold

The threshold for individual criteria is 3.

8.6 Consensus Report and Declaration

A form for collecting Declaration on Confidentiality and Conflict of Interest from Experts is available in APPENDIX B – Confidentiality and Conflict of Interest Declaration of this Deliverable.

9 Selected proposals: what to expect during the implementation.

This section explains the steps following the Open Call evaluation. Once the successful proposals have been selected through the previously detailed evaluation process, the Third Parties have to complete the negotiation process with the symbloTe Coordinator and sign an agreement prior to starting work and receiving funding from the project.

9.1 *Third Parties Agreement with the Coordinator*

In order to give full compliance to provision of art.15 GA - Rules for providing financial support to third parties, the symbloTe Consortium set up a specific Agreement to be signed by the selected Third Parties and the Coordinator. This agreement, named “symbloTe Standard Extension Contract” rules all the rights and obligations between Parties for the proper management of the Cascade Funding and its legal consequences. Due to the key importance that such documents represent for the management of fair and sound relationship between Third Parties and the Cascade Funding Partner (i.e. the symbloTe Coordinator), a further check will be performed during the implementation phase by the Legal Department of the Coordinator in order to ensure the maximum level of EU rules accomplishment. The material presented can therefore be subjected to modifications.

This agreement rules the following main specific items:

- Terms and conditions for the financial support
- Liability
- Intellectual Property Rights Policy
- Confidentiality
- Termination

In addition to the “symbloTe Standard Extension Contract”, a set of additional annexes have been prepared:

- ANNEX 1 - Grant Agreement specific obligations: this document contains GA obligations which accomplishment is mandatory for the Third Party using Cascade Funding, even if there are not accessing to the GA.
- ANNEX 2 - Technical Report Template: this document shall be used by the Third Party for reporting activities performed and costs incurred in order to access to scheduled payments.
- ANNEX 3 - Specific Extension Contract: this document describes the proposed extension under a technical and management point of view.

Those Annexes represent essential parts of the main agreement.

The Agreement between Selected Third Parties and the Coordinator and its Annexes is reported as APPENDIX A - symbloTe Standard Extension Contract to this deliverable.

9.2 Support during the implementation

Selected Third Parties will be supported during the implementation of the extension by symbloTe Partners. The Supporting Team (composed by a technical expert and a business expert) will be selected within the symbioTe Consortium according to the domain of the granted extension. It will follow for the whole duration of the extension the Third Party selected, providing support for technical/business aspects as well as the involvement of Third Parties in the activities of the Consortium and the symbloTe project (meetings, workshop, demonstration stages, involvement in the implementation phase).

It is expected that Third Parties meet in person with the symbloTe Consortium at least one time during the overall duration of the extension.

9.3 Payment Scheme: scheduled payment recommended

As a financial support provided by the Project to Selected Third Party, the following scheduled payments apply:

1. 30% of the overall financial support as advance payment after the signature of the Agreement with the Coordinator.
2. 30% of the overall financial support as interim payment based on the evaluation by the symbloTe consortium of the Intermediate Report, edited and provided by Selected Third Party approximately at the midpoint of the work planned.
3. 40% of the overall financial support as Final payment based on the evaluation by the symbloTe consortium of the Final Report, edited and provided by Selected Third Party at the end of the work planned and (eventually) following a formal approval of the report and the work at a Technical Project Review by the EC.

9.4 Reporting from Third Parties

The selected applicants will be linked to the symbloTe consortium as Associated Third Party to the Coordinator. In order to ensure the correct management of “Cascade Funding” for Third Parties (according to art. 15 MGA), the Coordinator requires the fulfilment of Reporting obligation as mandatory accomplishments for Scheduled Payments.

Two Reports need to be submitted on a timely basis to the coordinator:

1. Intermediate Report edited and provided by the Third Party at the midpoint of the work planned;
2. Final Report edited and provided by the Third Party at the conclusion of the work planned and eventually following a formal approval of the report and the work at a technical project review by the EC.

A specific template needs to be used and will include:

Part A. Summary

Part B. Detailed description - This section describes the details on the extension It includes:

- B.1 Concept, Objectives, Set-up and Background

- B.2 Technical Results
- B.3 Lessons learned
- B.4 Impact

Part C. Resources

- C.1 Resources Deployed
- C.2 Further development and exploitation

Part of these reports may be used by the symbloTe Consortium for inclusion in their reporting documents to the EC and in public presentations. Inclusion of confidential information should therefore be indicated and discussed with the symbloTe consortium.

These reports and extension's documentation will also be used for the formal review by the European Commission. The template for the Intermediary and Final Reports is available as Annex of the symbloTe Standard Extension Contract (Annex 2).

9.5 Access to foreground information from the project – IPR

This paragraph outlines the main information about Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) management for Third Parties. This basic information is meant to be provided in the Open Call Public announcement in order to give Third Parties an overview on how symbloTe Consortium intend to regulate Access to Background and to Foreground of symbloTe results. More detailed provisions on IPR, Access right and Confidentiality are provided in the symbloTe Standard Extension Contract.

9.5.1 IPR

Applicants chosen to participate in the Open Call, will become part of symbloTe Consortium as Associated Third Party to the Coordinator. In order to ensure the smooth running of the project activities and achievements, the Third Parties must declare what of their background will be made available to the project activities, and what is excluded or protected.

In accordance with section 9.7 of the Consortium Agreement of symbloTe, each partner has the right to revise the terms agreed for access to their background, **if it believes** that the entry of a new part can lead to conflicts of academic or commercial interests.

9.5.2 IP foreground (results) and general principle ownership

To ensure the expected impact of the Open call, applicants agree to make available to the symbloTe Consortium products results, to allow the continuity of exploitation and dissemination activities. The ownership of results is regulated by the section 8 of Consortium Agreement, that is based on the general concept "Results are owned by the party that generates them", foreseeing the joint ownership.

9.5.3 Access rights

Access Rights to background and results of project may be requested by the selected Third Party only if he needs the background for implementation of its tasks in the Open Call activities. In this case, the selected Third Party will have access rights to that

background for the duration of the Extension's activities on royalty-free basis, solely to the extent needed to implement its tasks;

In accomplishment to the Consortium Agreement signed by Partners, the access rights to background and results may be requested by the selected Third Party only if it needs such background for exploitation of results. In this case, the Third Party shall be granted access rights to such background on fair and reasonable conditions and upon separate written bilateral agreement between the selected Third Party and the owning partner. A request for access rights for exploitation may be made up to twelve months after the end of the Consortium Agreement.

9.5.4 Confidentiality

According with the article 36 of the Grant Agreement, all information which is disclosed in connection with the open call during its implementation and which has been marked as confidential, or disclosed orally has been identified as confidential at the time of disclosure, is confidential Information.

The applicants selected for the implementation of Extension activities, hereby undertake for the duration of the activities and a period of 4 years after the end of the Extension Standard Contract:

- not use confidential information otherwise than for the purpose for which it was disclosed;
- not disclose confidential information to any Third Party without the prior written consent by the disclosing party;
- the internal distribution of confidential information by a recipient to its employees shall take place on a strict need to know basis.

The recipients shall be responsible for the fulfilment of the above obligations on the part of their employees involved in the Open call, during and after the end of the project activities.

The restriction of confidential information is no longer applied if:

- the disclosing party agrees to release the other party;
- the information was already know by the recipient or is given to him without obligation of confidentiality by a third party that was not bound by any obligation of confidentiality;
- the recipient proves that the information was developed without the use of confidential information;
- the information becomes generally and publicly available, without breaching any confidentiality obligation;
- the disclosure of the information is required by EU or national law.

10 Conclusions and Next Steps

The deliverable D6.2 “2nd Open Call Text and Submission Template” describes the overall structure for managing the second symbloTe Open Call. During the issuing of this document, WP6 partners shared expertise and best practices in order to define the best solution in terms of procedures and overall objectives, according to specific needs and development progresses of the symbloTe project and previous Open Call experience. Very important input came also from the participation of several symbloTe partners to the activities of IoT-EPI meetings and common activities, as well as from past experiences of partners in applying to Open Calls.

The procedures and contents of this Deliverable represent the main structure for managing Open Calls and the closure of the design phase. The implementation phase that will bring to the public announcement of the Second Open Call (M22 – October 31, 2017) will see further improvements of the whole procedure and the issue of several documents, which will support applicants in submitting their proposal.

Next step related to this implementation phase will concern several issues, which will be coordinated within the Work Package 6, such as:

Task 6.1 - Open Calls Organization and Management

Finalization of the whole procedure and documentation for managing the Open Call process with the production and /or update of the following documents:

1. Call Announcement and Guidelines for Applicants update
2. Technical information for Applicants on Technical Aspects
3. Electronic Submission Guidelines update
4. Frequently Asked Question update
5. Notification Service activation
6. Pre-feasibility check service
7. Final Legal check on Agreements with Third Parties

Task 6.2 - Open Calls Evaluation

The Evaluation Procedure has been set up for the first Open Call. The procedure will see some minor adaptation needed for the different focus and scope of the second Open Call. The implementation phase will finalise the necessary steps to select external experts and will prepare the following documentation:

1. Evaluation guidelines
2. Briefing Package for External Experts involved in the Evaluation

Task 6.3 - Open Calls Impact

This Task foresees the deployment of activities aiming at keeping Open Calls communication activities aligned with the overall strategy developed in WP7 in order to widen the possible impact within the IoT Communities. During the first Open Call main indicators for Impact assessment has been defined as follows:

1. Expression of interest
2. N. of application received
3. Publication/Press release
4. Consortium professional contacts

5. Association/communities contacts
6. Webinar attendees
7. Web page visits
8. Technical impact created by Third Parties

The initial assessment has been realised. Next steps will concern the monitoring and the realisation of the D6.4 - Report on Open Call and Contest Impact.

11 APPENDICES

APPENDIX A - symbloTe Standard Extension Contract

APPENDIX B – Confidentiality and Conflict of Interest Declaration

APPENDIX A - symbloTe Standard Extension Contract

symbloTe Standard Extension Contract

for the Research and Innovation Action

symbloTe: *Symbiosis of smart objects across IoT environments*

Project Number: 688156

G02/xx/xxxx

under the “Horizon 2020 – the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)” of the European Commission

The symbloTe Consortium

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symbloTe Standard Extension Contract

This symbloTe Standard Extension Contract for providing financial support to the Selected Third Party, hereinafter referred to as the “Agreement”, is entered into by and between:

INTRACOM S.A. TELECOM SOLUTIONS (“Cascade Funding Partner”), a company incorporated under the laws of Greece, having its registered office at 19.7km Markopoulou Ave., 19002, Peania, Attica, Greece herein represented by Mr Anastasios Dimopoulos, General Manager and Mr Anastasios Athanasopoulos, Bidding & Contracting Section Manager

And

_____ (**“Selected Third Party”**), an organization under the laws of _____ having its registered office at _____, with VAT No _____, herein represented by _____

Hereinafter sometimes individually referred to as **“Party”** and collectively referred to as **“Parties”**.

Whereas INTRACOM SA TELECOM SOLUTIONS (ICOM) AE, 234549, established in Greece, having its registered offices at NEW ROAD PEANIA MARKOPOULO 19 7KM, PEANIA 19002, ATTICA, Greece, EL094157119, SVEUCILISTE U ZAGREBU FAKULTET ELEKTROTEHNIKE I RACUNARSTVA (UNIZG-FER), 080159989, established in UNSKA 3, ZAGREB 10000, Croatia, HR57029260362, AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH (AIT) GMBH, FN115980I, established in Donau-City-Strasse 1, WIEN 1220, Austria, ATU14703506,, NEXTWORKS (NXW) SRL, 01628570507, established in VIA LIVORNESE 1027, PISA 56122, Italy, IT01628570507, CONSORZIO NAZIONALE INTERUNIVERSITARIO PER LE TELECOMUNICAZIONI (CNIT) IT4, REA 220619 PARMA, established in VIALE G. P. USBERTI 181A, PARMA 43124, Italy, IT01938560347, ATOS SPAIN SA (ATOS) SA, M64516, established in Calle de Albarracin 25, Madrid 28037, Spain, ESA28240752, UNIVERSITAT WIEN (UNIVIE), established in UNIVERSITATSRING 1, WIEN 1010, Austria, ATU37586901, UNIDATA SPA (UNIDATA) SPA, 956645CF06187081002, established in VIA PORTUENSE 1555, ROMA 00148, Italy, IT06187081002, SENSING & CONTROL SYSTEMS SL (S&C) SL, B337567, established in AVENIDA PAISOS CATALANS 71 BAIXOS, IGUALADA 08700, Spain, ESB64305402, FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV (IOSB) EV, VR4461, established in HANSASTRASSE 27C, MUNCHEN 80686, Germany, DE129515865, UBIWHERE Lda (UW) LDA, 508245567, established in RUA PEDRO VAZ DE ECA 6, Aveiro 3800 322, Portugal, PT508245567, VIPNET DRUSTVO Z OGRANICENOM ODGOVORNOSCU ZA USLUGE JAVNIH TELEKOMUNIKACIJA (VIP) DOO, 080253268, established in VRTNI PUT 1, ZAGREB 10000, Croatia, HR29524210204, INSTYTUT CHEMII BIOORGANICZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK (PSNC), 000849327, established in NOSKOWSKIEGO 12-14, POZNAN 61 704, Poland, PL7770002062, NA.VI.GO. SOCIETA CONSORTILE A RESPONSABILITA LIMITATA (NAVIGO) SCARL, 194941, established in VIA MICHELE COPPINO 116, VIAREGGIO 55049, Italy, IT02077140461, UNIVERSITAT ZURICH (UZH), CH35070002082, established in RAMISTRASSE 71, ZURICH 8006, Switzerland, CH233525 (hereinafter sometimes individually or collectively referred as **“symbloTe Beneficiary”** or the **“symbloTe Beneficiaries”**) participate to the H2020 project entitled **“Symbiosis of smart objects across IoT environments”** (hereinafter the **“symbloTe Project”**).

Whereas the symbloTe Beneficiaries entered into a Grant Agreement N° 688156 with the European Commission (the “Grant Agreement” or “GA”) and signed together in 2016 a

Consortium Agreement with respect to the symbloTe Project (the “Consortium Agreement” or “CA”).

Whereas the symbloTe Project involves financial support to Third Parties through a Cascade Funding scheme (hereinafter “Cascade Funding”) according to art. 15 - GA.

Whereas further to an open call for a specific Extension as described in Annex 3 “Specific Extension Contract”, the Selected Third Party has been selected by the Evaluation Committee of the symbloTe Project to implement such Extension.

Whereas the Cascade Funding Partner (the symbloTe Coordinator) is willing to provide financial support to the Selected Third Party for the implementation of such Extension and the Selected Third Party is willing to receive such funding under the terms and conditions of this Agreement.

Whereas in accordance with the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, the Cascade Funding Partner shall sign the symbloTe Standard Extension Contract (hereinafter the Agreement) with the Selected Third Party compliant with the GA and CA.

Whereas the Cascade Funding Partner is responsible for the execution of this Agreement with the Selected Third Party and for the monitoring of the Agreement.

Now therefore it has been agreed as follows:

Section 1: Definitions

Words beginning with a capital letter shall have the meaning defined in the preamble of the Agreement or in this Section:

1.1. Access Rights means rights to use Results or Background under the terms and conditions laid down in this Agreement.

1.2. An Affiliated Entity of a symbloTe Beneficiary means:

- a) any legal entity directly or indirectly Controlling, Controlled by, or under common Control with that symbloTe Beneficiary, for so long as such Control lasts; and
- b) any other legal entity being an Affiliated Entity of a symbloTe Beneficiary, where such legal entity is one in which that symbloTe Beneficiary (or a legal entity qualifying as an Affiliated Entity of that symbloTe Beneficiary under (a) directly above) has a 50% equity share or is the single largest equity shareholder.

For the above purposes, "Control" of any legal entity shall exist through the direct or indirect:

- ownership of more than 50% of the nominal value of the issued share capital of the legal entity or of more than 50% of the issued share capital entitling the holders to vote for the election of directors or persons performing similar functions, or
- right by any other means to elect or appoint directors of the legal entity (or persons performing similar functions) who have a majority vote.

Common Control through government does not, in itself, create Affiliated Entity status.

1.3. Agreement means this symbloTe Standard Extension Contract, together with its Annexes.

1.4. Background means any data, know-how or information – whatever its form or nature (tangible or intangible), including any rights such as intellectual property rights – that:

- a) is held by a Participating Partner **before 1 January 2016**, and
- b) is Needed by another Participating Partner to implement its own tasks under the Extension or to Exploit its own Results, but solely to the extent that such data,

information, know-how and/or intellectual property rights are introduced into the Extension by its owner.

1.5. Exploitation or Exploit means the direct or indirect use of Results in (a) further research activities other than those covered by the Extension, or (b) in developing, creating or marketing a product or process, or (c) in creating and providing a service, or (d) in standardization activities.

1.6. Fair and Reasonable conditions means appropriate conditions, including possible financial terms or royalty-free conditions, taking into account the specific circumstances of the request for Access Rights, for example the actual or potential value of the Results or Background to which Access Rights are requested and/or the scope, duration and other characteristics of the exploitation envisaged. To fall within Fair and Reasonable conditions, the conditions must also be non-discriminatory.

With respect to symbloTe Beneficiaries which are Non-Profit Organizations considering their specific positioning, “appropriate conditions” means that, if requested by such Non-Profit Organizations, they will receive a financial compensation in case of direct or indirect industrial or commercial exploitation of their own Results.

1.7. Feedback means, in the course of or in connection with the Extension, all comments, ideas for improvements or for modifications, information about use and performance, suggestions or other feedback from any Party or the Selected Third Party regarding a Platform Partner’s products or technology used in the Extension.

1.8. Financial Support means the cash element of the financial support to be given by the Cascade Funding Partner to the Selected Third Party for the implementation of the Extension as detailed in Annex 3 “Specific Extension Contract”.

1.9. Extension means the work detailed in Annex 3 “Specific Extension Contract” to be carried out by the Selected Third Party, with the objective to develop a symbloTe compliant extension.

1.10. Participating Partners means the entities and organizations participating in the Extension, being: (a) the Selected Third Party, (b) the Cascade Funding Partner, (c) any other symbloTe Beneficiary.

1.11. Industrial Party means a symbloTe Beneficiary which is not a Non-Profit Organization.

1.12. Intellectual Property Rights Policy means the Policy set out at Section 5 of this Agreement.

1.13. Needed means in respect of executing or carrying out the Extension, and/or in respect of Exploitation of Results, technically essential and:

- a. where intellectual property rights are concerned, that those intellectual property rights would be infringed without Access Rights being granted under this Agreement;
- b. where Confidential Information is concerned, only Confidential Information which has been disclosed during the Extension may be considered as technically essential, except as otherwise agreed in writing between the Participating Partners.

- 1.14. Non-Profit Organization** means a legal entity that is by its legal form non-profit-making or has a legal or statutory obligation not to distribute profits to its shareholders or individual members.
- 1.15. Results** means any tangible or intangible outputs of the Extension, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the Extension, as well as any rights attached to them, including intellectual property rights.

Section 2: Conditions from the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement reflected in the Agreement

The Cascade Funding Partner receives funding from the European Commission for organizing the selection of Third Parties through Open Calls. Under the symbloTe Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, some of the obligations have to be imposed on the Selected Third Party. Those obligations are reflected in this Agreement. The specific obligations that the Selected Third Party must ensure as described in the Grant Agreement are reproduced in Annex 1.

The Selected Third Party acknowledges and agrees that these obligations comprised in this Agreement are fully applicable to it and shall do everything that is necessary to comply with these obligations.

Section 3: Terms and Conditions for the Financial Support

- 3.1.** The Selected Third Party shall take part in the Extension in accordance with the state of the art. The Selected Third Party shall carry out the tasks according to the schedule set forth in Annex 3 "Specific Extension Contract" at the latest and shall report to the Cascade Funding Partner on the activities' progress in regular intervals as indicated in Annex 3 "Specific Extension Contract". Such technical reports based on the template provided in Annex 2 shall contain detailed information on the results generated by the Selected Third Party.
- 3.2.** The Cascade Funding Partner shall give Financial Support for the Extension carried out by the Selected Third Party, within the limits and in accordance with the schedule of payments specified in Annex 3 "Specific Extension Contract".
- 3.3.** The Selected Third Party shall be entitled to claim eligible costs for the Extension as described in Annex 2 of this Agreement. The financial support takes the form of a reimbursement of eligible costs and is equal to the amount of EUR _____. As a financial support provided by the Project to Selected Third Party, the following scheduled payments apply:
- 40% of the overall financial support as advance payment after the signature of this Agreement with the Coordinator.
 - 30% of the overall financial support as interim payment based on the evaluation by the symbloTe consortium of the Intermediate Report, edited and provided by Selected Third Party by midterm (after half of the Extension's duration has passed from the Extension starting date).
 - 30% of the overall financial support as Final payment subject to the evaluation by the symbloTe Consortium of Final Report, edited and provided by Selected

Third Party at the end of the Extension's duration and (eventually) following a formal approval of the report and the work at a Technical Project Review by the EC.

3.4. The Selected Third Party shall provide two Reports on performed activities and related costs report to the Cascade Funding Partner. The Selected Third Party shall use the reporting template in Annex 2. The following elements shall at least be included in these costs reports :

- a) The identification of the Extension ;
- b) Detailed information on technical results and further development
- c) Detailed information and documentation on the costs incurred for the implementation of the Extension that permit justification of the eligibility of the costs.

No payment will be done by the Cascade Funding Partner if no sufficient evidence document is presented by the Selected Third Party and relevantly approved. As mentioned in above art. 3.3, two reports are planned:

- a) Intermediate Report: by midterm (after half of the Extension's duration has passed from the Extension starting date);
- b) Final Report: at the end of the Extension's duration and (eventually) following a formal approval of the report and the work at a Technical Project Review by the EC.

3.5. The Cascade Funding Partner will transfer the amount of the Financial Support to the Selected Third Party on the basis of (i) a written payment request by the Selected Third Party to be sent to the Cascade Funding Partner together with an invoice, if applicable, in accordance with the schedule set forth in Annex 3 "Specific Extension Contract" and (ii) a decision of the Cascade Funding Partner for awarding the amount to the Selected Third Party, provided the terms and conditions of this Agreement are complied with, in particular after the written validation by the Cascade Funding Partner of the corresponding deliverable(s) identified in Annex 3 "Specific Extension Contract". The payment shall be made as indicated in Annex 3 "Specific Extension Contract" after the written validation of the payment request by the Cascade Funding Partner however always provided that the conditions listed in this Section 3 are met by the Selected Third Party. In turn, the Selected Third Party should send a written acknowledgement upon the reception of the payment.

3.6. The Selected Third Party is aware that if the Cascade Funding Partner is required to make any deduction or withholding on account of any taxes ("Withholding Tax") from the amount payable to the Selected Third Party, then the Cascade Funding Partner shall make the relevant deduction or withholding from the amount due to the Selected Third Party. The Cascade Funding Partner shall i) promptly pay to the relevant authority within the relevant period permitted by law the full amount of such deduction or withholding and ii) provide the Selected Third Party with written evidence (including certification where appropriate) that it has made the payment to the relevant tax authority.

3.7. The collaboration between Selected Third Party and Cascade Funding Partner will last maximum six (6) months. The start date of the Extension is [start date] and the end date is [end date].

Section 4: Liability

- 4.1.** The Selected Third Party shall comply with all applicable laws, rules and regulations, including, but not limited to safety, security, welfare, social security and fiscal laws, rules and regulations.
- 4.2.** The Selected Third Party shall not be entitled to act or to make legally binding declarations on behalf of the Cascade Funding Partner and/or any other symbloTe Beneficiary and shall fully indemnify all of the latter from any third party claim resulting from a breach of these obligations.
- 4.3.** The total contractual liability of the Cascade Funding Partner for any reason whatsoever and howsoever arising out of and/or in connection with this Agreement shall in any case be limited to the amount of the Financial Support provided to the Selected Third Party hereunder. The Cascade Funding Partner shall not in any case be liable for any indirect, incidental, punitive, special and/ or consequential damages and losses including but not limited to :
- loss of profits, interest, savings, production and business opportunities;
 - loss of contracts, goodwill, and anticipated savings;
 - loss of or damage to reputation or to data;
 - costs of recall of products.
- 4.4.** This limitation of liability shall not apply in cases of willful act or gross negligence.
- 4.5.** The Selected Third Party shall fully and exclusively bear the risks and has any and all liabilities arising out of and/or in connection with the Extension for which Financial Support is granted by the Cascade Funding Partner. The Selected Third Party shall indemnify the symbloTe Beneficiaries and the Cascade Funding Partner for any and all damages, losses, penalties, costs and expenses which the symbloTe Beneficiaries and/or the Cascade Funding Partner would incur or have to pay to the European Commission and/or to any third parties with respect to such Extension financially supported and/or for any damages and losses in general which the symbloTe Beneficiaries or the Cascade Funding Partner incur as a result thereof. In addition, should the European Commission have a right to recovery against the Cascade Funding Partner or another symbloTe Beneficiary regarding the Financial Support granted under this Agreement, the Selected Third Party shall pay the sums in question, in the terms and the date specified by the Cascade Funding Partner. Moreover, the Selected Third Party shall indemnify and hold the symbloTe Beneficiaries and the Cascade Funding Partner, their respective officers, directors, employees and agents harmless from and against all repayments, loss, liability, costs, charges, claims or damages that result from or arising out of any such recovery action by the European Commission.
- 4.6.** In respect of any information or materials (including Results and Background) supplied by one Party to another Party or to a symbloTe Beneficiary, or by a symbloTe Beneficiary involved in the applicable Extension to a Party, no warranty or representation of any kind is made, given or implied as to the sufficiency, accuracy or fitness for purpose nor as to the absence of any infringement of any proprietary rights of third parties. Therefore,
- the recipient, shall in all cases be entirely and solely liable for the use to which it puts such information and materials (including Results and Background), and

- there is no liability in case of infringement of proprietary rights of a third party resulting from any Access Rights.

Section 5: Intellectual Property Rights Policy

The Selected Third Party acknowledges the terms of the “Intellectual Property Rights Policy” defined hereinafter. The Selected Third Party agrees that it will comply with the Intellectual Property Rights Policy to ensure that the Cascade Funding Partner will always be able to comply with such terms towards the other symbloTe Beneficiaries.

5.1 General Principle regarding Ownership

Results are owned by the Party or by the symbloTe Beneficiary that generates them.

5.2 Joint Results

As requested in the Consortium Agreement signed between the symbloTe Beneficiaries, among which the Cascade Funding Partner, if, in the course of carrying out the Extension, a Result is generated by the Selected Third Party with one or several symbloTe Beneficiaries (the “Contributors”), and if the contributions to or features of such Result form an indivisible part thereof to the extent that none of the said Contributors could reasonably claim full ownership of this Result, such Result shall be jointly owned by them in equal shares, unless differently agreed by the Contributors.

Where such joint Result is covered by intellectual property rights, the Contributors shall execute a joint ownership agreement regarding the allocation and the conditions of exploitation of the joint Result as soon as possible. They shall do all their best efforts to execute such joint ownership agreement at the **latest six (6) months** after the beginning of the industrial or commercial exploitation of such joint Result.

The Contributors shall agree on all protection measures, on their joint ownership shares and on the division of related costs in a joint ownership agreement to be negotiated.

Unless otherwise agreed in the joint ownership agreement:

- each of the Contributors shall be entitled to use their jointly owned Results for internal research activities on a royalty-free basis including for internal educational activities, and without requiring the prior consent of the other Contributors subject to confidentiality obligations, and
- the Contributors shall be entitled to otherwise exploit the jointly owned Results and to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties (without any right to sub-license), if the other Contributors are given:
 - a) at least 45 calendar days advance notice; and
 - b) Fair and Reasonable compensation.

With respect to the “Fair and Reasonable compensation” due to the Selected Third Party which are Non-Profit Organizations, considering their specific positioning, “Fair and Reasonable compensation” means, if requested by such Non-Profit Organizations, that they will receive a financial compensation in case of direct or indirect exploitation of joint Results.

The Parties expressly agree herein that in case of joint ownership between Industrial Parties, such Industrial Parties are entitled to directly Exploit their joint Result without

asking the other Industrial Parties' approval and without paying any compensation to the other Industrial Parties.

5.3 Access Rights

For the purpose of this article 5.3, Background shall mean the Background as listed in the Annex 3 "Specific Extension Contract" and validated by the Participating Partners for the concerned Extension.

Access Rights to Background and to the Results of the Grant Agreement may be requested by the Selected Third Party only from the Cascade Funding Partner, only if the following conditions are fulfilled:

- The Selected Third Party Needs such listed Background for implementation of its tasks in the Extension. Where this is the case, the Selected Third Party will have Access Rights to that Background for the duration of the Extension on royalty-free basis, solely to the extent Needed to implement its tasks in the Extension;

Due to provisions of the consortium agreement signed between the symbloTe Beneficiaries, Access Rights to Background and Results may be requested by the Selected Third Party only from the Participating Partner, only in the following case and if the following conditions are fulfilled:

- The Selected Third Party Needs such listed Background for Exploitation of its own Extension Results. Where this is the case and subject to the limitations stated in the Specific Extension Contract, the Selected Third Party shall be granted Access Rights to such Background on Fair and Reasonable conditions and upon separate written bilateral agreement between the Selected Third Party and the owning Participating Partner. A request for Access Rights for Exploitation may be made up to twelve months after the end of the Extension.
- The symbloTe Beneficiaries involved in the Extension enjoy the same Access Rights on Background or Results owned by the Selected Third Party for implementation of the Extension or, direct or indirect exploitation of their Results, under the same conditions mentioned here above.

For the avoidance of doubt, any grant of Access Rights not covered by this Section shall be at the absolute discretion of the owner and subject to such terms and conditions as may be agreed between the owner and recipient.

Section 6: Confidentiality

All information of whatever nature and in whatever form or mode of communication, which is disclosed by a Party (the "Disclosing Party") to another Party (the "Recipient") in connection with the Extension during its implementation and which has been explicitly marked as "confidential" at the time of disclosure, or when disclosed orally has been identified as confidential at the time of disclosure and has been confirmed and designated in writing within fifteen (15) calendar days from oral disclosure at the latest as confidential information by the Disclosing Party, is "Confidential Information".

The Recipients hereby undertake for the duration of the Extension and a period of 4 years after the end of the Extension:

- not to use Confidential Information otherwise than for the purpose for which it was disclosed;
- not to disclose Confidential Information to any third party without the prior written consent by the Disclosing Party;

- to ensure that internal distribution of Confidential Information by a Recipient to its employees shall take place on a strict need-to-know basis; and
- except as required for continuing Access Rights, to return to the Disclosing Party on demand all Confidential Information which has been supplied to or acquired by the Recipients including all copies thereof and to delete all information stored in a machine readable form. The Recipients may keep a copy to the extent it is required to keep, archive or store such Confidential Information because of compliance with applicable mandatory laws and regulations (i.e. public policy legislation).

The Recipients shall be responsible for the fulfillment of the above obligations on the part of their employees involved in the Extension and shall ensure that they remain so obliged, as far as legally possible, during and after the end of the Extension and/or after the termination of the contractual relationship with the employee or third party.

The above shall not apply for disclosure or use of Confidential Information, if and in so far as the Recipient can show that:

- the Confidential Information becomes publicly available by means other than a breach of the Recipient's confidentiality obligations;
- the Disclosing Party subsequently informs the Recipient that the Confidential Information is no longer confidential;
- the Confidential Information is communicated to the Recipient without any obligation of confidence by a third party who is to the best knowledge of the Recipient in lawful possession thereof and under no obligation of confidence to the Disclosing Party;
- the disclosure or communication of the Confidential Information is foreseen by provisions of the Grant Agreement;
- the Confidential Information, at any time, was developed by the Recipient completely independently of any such disclosure by the Disclosing Party; or
- the Confidential Information was already known to the Recipient prior to disclosure or
- the Recipient is required to disclose the Confidential Information in order to comply with applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order subject to the last paragraph of this Section.

The Recipient shall apply the same degree of care with regard to the Confidential Information disclosed within the scope of the Extension as with its own confidential and/or proprietary information, but in no case less than reasonable care.

Each Recipient or Disclosing Party shall promptly advise the other Recipient or Disclosing Party in writing of any unauthorized disclosure, misappropriation or misuse of Confidential Information after it becomes aware of such unauthorized disclosure, misappropriation or misuse.

If a Recipient becomes aware that it will be required to disclose Confidential Information in order to comply with applicable laws or regulations or with a court or administrative order, it shall, to the extent it is lawfully able to do so, prior to any such disclosure:

- notify the Disclosing Party of said request, and
- comply to the extent possible with the Disclosing Party's reasonable instructions to protect the confidentiality of the information at the Disclosing Party's expense, and
- make such disclosure only to the extent it is compelled.

As far as Cascade Funding Partner is concerned, disclosure of Confidential Information to the European Commission shall be governed by the terms of the GA.

As far as Selected Third Party is concerned, disclosure of Confidential Information to or from another Participating Partner (other than the Cascade Funding Partner) shall be governed by the terms of a specific non-disclosure agreement to be signed between them.

Section 7: Dissemination

Each Party agrees that any dissemination activity (including publications, presentations or contributions to any standards organisation) by the Selected Third Party is subject to the prior written approval of the other Participating Partners.

The Cascade Funding Partner and the other Participating Partners are entitled to include the main issues and information regarding the Extension in their reporting towards the European Commission, subject to prior written notification to the Selected Third Party.

Section 8: Checks and Audits

The Selected Third Party undertakes to provide any detailed information, including information in electronic format, requested by the European Commission or by any other outside body authorized by the European Commission to check that the Extension and the provisions of this Agreement are being properly implemented.

The Selected Third Party shall keep at the European Commission disposal all original documents, especially accounting and tax records, or, in exceptional and duly justified cases, certified copies of original documents relating to the Agreement, stored on any appropriate medium that ensures their integrity in accordance with the applicable national legislation, for a period of five years from the date of payment of the balance specified in the grant agreements.

The Selected Third Party agrees that the European Commission may have an audit of the use made of the Financial Support carried out either directly by the European Commission staff or by any other outside body authorized to do so on its behalf. Such audits may be carried out throughout the period of implementation of the Agreement until the balance is paid and for a period of five years from the date of payment of the balance. Where appropriate, the audit findings may lead to recovery decisions by the European Commission. The Selected Third Party undertakes to allow European Commission staff and outside personnel authorized by the European Commission the appropriate right of access to the sites and premises of the Selected Third Party and to all the information, including information in electronic format, needed in order to conduct such audits.

In accordance with Union legislation, the European Commission, the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF) and the European Court of Auditors (ECA) may carry out spot checks and inspections of the documents of the Selected Third Party, and of any recipient of Cascade Finding, including at the premises of the Selected Third Party, in accordance with the procedures laid down by Union law for the protection of the financial interests of the Union against fraud and other irregularities. Where appropriate, the inspection findings may lead to recovery decisions by the European Commission. The Articles 22 and 23 of the Grant Agreement, reproduced in Annex 1, also apply to the Selected Third Party.

Section 9: Termination

The Cascade Funding Partner can terminate this Agreement harmless for itself with immediate effect through written notice to the Selected Third Party and to the other Participating Partners:

- 9.1.** if the Selected Third Party is in breach of any of its material obligations under this Agreement, which breach is not remediable, or, if remediable, has not been remedied within thirty (30) days after written notice to that effect from the party not in breach,
- 9.2.** if, to the extent permitted by law, the Selected Third Party is declared bankrupt, is being wound up, is having its affairs administered by the courts, has entered into an

arrangement with its creditors, has suspended business activities, or is the subject of any other similar proceeding concerning those matters, or

- 9.3.** if the Selected Third Party is subject to an Event of Force Majeure, which prevents the Selected Third Party from correct performance of its obligations hereunder and such circumstances have lasted, or can reasonably be expected to last more than 3 months.
- 9.4.** In any case of termination of the Grant Agreement and/or the Consortium Agreement, for any reason whatsoever and howsoever.
- 9.5.** In any case of expiration or termination of the present, the Cascade Funding Partner's sole liability shall be to give to the Selected Third Party Financial Support for the Extension (or part of it) which the European Commission has formally approved.
- 9.6.** Access Rights granted to the Selected Third Party shall cease immediately upon the effective date of termination.

Section 10: Concluding Conditions

- 10.1.** The Selected Third Party's consistent level in its respective field of expertise played a key role in the selection of the Selected Third Parties to implement the Extension. Any total or partial transfer of provisions and the rights and duties it entails in the prior formal approval of all signatories.
- 10.2.** The Selected Third Party shall not, without prior written consent of the Cascade Funding Partner, assign the Agreement or any part of the project, or assign, mortgage, charge or encumber any benefit whatsoever arising or which may arise under the Agreement. Such assignment may only be consented to by the Cascade Funding Partner.

The Selected Third Party shall not, without prior written consent of the Cascade Funding Partner, subcontract any part of the Agreement. The Selected Third Party shall secure that the subcontractor will comply with all obligations – especially coming from the Grant Agreement, and with regard to confidentiality – resulting from this Agreement and that the results attained by the subcontractor will be available in accordance with Section 5 of this Agreement.

In any event, the Selected Third Party shall not be relieved from his responsibility under the Agreement for such parts of the Agreement as are subcontracted and the Selected Third Party shall be responsible and liable for the acts or defaults of any subcontractor or their employees, servants and agents, as fully as if they were the acts or defaults of the Selected Third Party or the Selected Third Party's employees, servants and agents.

Any assignment, mortgage, charge, encumbrance or subcontract in contravention of this clause shall, as against the Cascade Funding Partner, be void and of no effect, and may be ignored by the Cascade Funding Partner.

The Selected Third Party shall protect, defend, indemnify and keep the Cascade Funding Partner indemnified against all claims, demands, actions, suits, proceedings, writs, judgment, orders, decrees, damages, losses and expenses suffered or incurred by the Cascade Funding Partner arising out of or related to such assignment, mortgage, charge, encumbrance or subcontract..

- 10.3.** If any provision of this Agreement is determined to be illegal or in conflict with the applicable law, the validity of the remaining provisions shall not be affected. The ineffective provision shall be replaced by an effective provision which is economically equivalent. The same shall apply in case of a gap.

- 10.4.** This Agreement shall be binding on the Selected Third Party and on the Cascade Funding Partner and their respective successors and their permitted assigns.
- 10.5.** Any dispute arising out of or in connection with this Extension, including any question regarding its existence, validity or termination, shall be referred to and finally resolved by arbitration under the LCIA Rules, which Rules are deemed to be incorporated by reference into this clause. The number of arbitrators shall be three. The seat, or legal place, of arbitration shall be Brussels, Belgium.
 The language to be used in the arbitral proceedings shall be the English language.
 The governing law of the Extension, shall be the law of Belgium, without reference to its conflicts of law provisions.

Section 11: Annexes

Annex 1: Grant Agreement Specific Obligations
Annex 2 : Technical report template
Annex 3 - Specific Extension Contract
are attached to the present and constitute an integral part thereof.

Section 12: Signatures

Done in two originals, one for each Party.

Cascade Funding Partner

Selected Third Party

Name:
Title:
Date:

Name:
Title:
Date:

Annex 1: Grant Agreement Specific Obligations

The Selected Third Party has to fulfill the obligations described in article 22, 23, 35, 36, 38 and 46 of the Grant Agreement. These sections are part of the Agreement. In case of contradiction between these sections and the Agreement, the terms of the Agreement will prevail. For completeness, any other sections referenced by the aforementioned articles can be found in the H2020 Annotated Model Grant Agreement, available from the following link:

http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf

In this Annex 1, the term “**action**” means “**Extension**”, the term “**beneficiary**” means “**Selected Third Party**” and the term “**grant**” means “**Extension**”.

ARTICLE 22 — CHECKS, REVIEWS, AUDITS AND INVESTIGATIONS — EXTENSION OF FINDINGS

22.1 Checks, reviews and audits by the Commission

22.1.1 Right to carry out checks

The Commission will — during the implementation of the action or afterwards — check the proper implementation of the action and compliance with the obligations under the Agreement, including assessing deliverables and reports.

For this purpose the Commission may be assisted by external persons or bodies.

The Commission may also request additional information in accordance with Article 17. The Commission may request beneficiaries to provide such information to it directly.

Information provided must be accurate, precise and complete and in the format requested, including electronic format.

22.1.2 Right to carry out reviews

The Commission may — during the implementation of the action or afterwards — carry out reviews on the proper implementation of the action (including assessment of deliverables and reports), compliance with the obligations under the Agreement and continued scientific or technological relevance of the action.

Reviews may be started **up to two years after the payment of the balance**. They will be formally notified to the coordinator or beneficiary concerned and will be considered to have started on the date of the formal notification.

If the review is carried out on a third party (see Articles 10 to 16), the beneficiary concerned must inform the third party.

The Commission may carry out reviews directly (using its own staff) or indirectly (using external persons or bodies appointed to do so). It will inform the coordinator or beneficiary concerned of the identity of the external persons or bodies. They have the right to object to the appointment on grounds of commercial confidentiality.

The coordinator or beneficiary concerned must provide — within the deadline requested — any information and data in addition to deliverables and reports already submitted (including information on the use of resources). The Commission may request beneficiaries to provide such information to it directly.

The coordinator or beneficiary concerned may be requested to participate in meetings, including with external experts.

For **on-the-spot** reviews, the beneficiaries must allow access to their sites and premises, including to external persons or bodies, and must ensure that information requested is readily available.

Information provided must be accurate, precise and complete and in the format requested, including electronic format.

On the basis of the review findings, a '**review report**' will be drawn up.

The Commission will formally notify the review report to the coordinator or beneficiary concerned, which has 30 days to formally notify observations ('**contradictory review procedure**').

Reviews (including review reports) are in the language of the Agreement.

22.1.3 Right to carry out audits

The Commission may — during the implementation of the action or afterwards — carry out audits on the proper implementation of the action and compliance with the obligations under the Agreement.

Audits may be started **up to two years after the payment of the balance**. They will be formally notified to the coordinator or beneficiary concerned and will be considered to have started on the date of the formal notification.

If the audit is carried out on a third party (see Articles 10 to 16), the beneficiary concerned must inform the third party.

The Commission may carry out audits directly (using its own staff) or indirectly (using external persons or bodies appointed to do so). It will inform the coordinator or beneficiary concerned of the identity of the external persons or bodies. They have the right to object to the appointment on grounds of commercial confidentiality.

The coordinator or beneficiary concerned must provide — within the deadline requested — any information (including complete accounts, individual salary statements or other personal data) to verify compliance with the Agreement. The Commission may request beneficiaries to provide such information to it directly.

For **on-the-spot** audits, the beneficiaries must allow access to their sites and premises, including to external persons or bodies, and must ensure that information requested is readily available.

Information provided must be accurate, precise and complete and in the format requested, including electronic format.

On the basis of the audit findings, a 'draft audit report' will be drawn up.

The Commission will formally notify the draft audit report to the coordinator or beneficiary concerned, which has 30 days to formally notify observations ('contradictory audit procedure'). This period may be extended by the Commission in justified cases.

The '**final audit report**' will take into account observations by the coordinator or beneficiary concerned. The report will be formally notified to it.

Audits (including audit reports) are in the language of the Agreement.

The Commission may also access the beneficiaries' statutory records for the periodical assessment of unit costs or flat-rate amounts.

22.2 Investigations by the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF)

Under Regulations No 883/2013³ and No 2185/96⁴ (and in accordance with their provisions and procedures), the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF) may — at any moment during implementation of the action or afterwards — carry out investigations, including on-the-spot checks and inspections, to establish whether there has been fraud, corruption or any other illegal activity affecting the financial interests of the EU.

22.3 Checks and audits by the European Court of Auditors (ECA)

Under Article 287 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) and Article 161 of the Financial Regulation No 966/2012⁵, the European Court of Auditors (ECA) may — at any moment during implementation of the action or afterwards — carry out audits.

The ECA has the right of access for the purpose of checks and audits.

22.4 Checks, reviews, audits and investigations for international organisations

Not applicable

22.5 Consequences of findings in checks, reviews, audits and investigations — Extension of findings

22.5.1 Findings in this grant

Findings in checks, reviews, audits or investigations carried out in the context of this grant may lead to the rejection of ineligible costs (see Article 42), reduction of the grant (see Article 43), recovery of undue amounts (see Article 44) or to any of the other measures described in Chapter 6.

Rejection of costs or reduction of the grant after the payment of the balance will lead to a revised final grant amount (see Article 5.4).

Findings in checks, reviews, audits or investigations may lead to a request for amendment for the modification of Annex 2 (see Article 55).

Checks, reviews, audits or investigations that find systemic or recurrent errors, irregularities, fraud or breach of obligations may also lead to consequences in other EU or Euratom grants awarded under similar conditions (**'extension of findings from this grant to other grants'**).

Moreover, findings arising from an OLAF investigation may lead to criminal prosecution under national law.

22.5.2 Findings in other grants

The Commission may extend findings from other grants to this grant ('extension of findings from other grants to this grant'), if:

- (a) the beneficiary concerned is found, in other EU or Euratom grants awarded under similar conditions, to have committed systemic or recurrent errors, irregularities, fraud or breach of obligations that have a material impact on this grant and
- (b) those findings are formally notified to the beneficiary concerned — together with the list of grants affected by the findings — no later than two years after the payment of the balance of this grant.

³ Regulation (EU, Euratom) No 883/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 September 2013 concerning investigations conducted by the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF) and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1073/1999 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Regulation (Euratom) No 1074/1999 (OJ L 248, 18.09.2013, p. 1).

⁴ Council Regulation (Euratom, EC) No 2185/1996 of 11 November 1996 concerning on-the-spot checks and inspections carried out by the Commission in order to protect the European Communities' financial interests against fraud and other irregularities (OJ L 292, 15.11.1996, p. 2).

⁵ Regulation (EU, Euratom) No 966/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on the financial rules applicable to the general budget of the Union and repealing Council Regulation (EC, Euratom) No 1605/2002 (OJ L 298, 26.10.2012, p. 1).

The extension of findings may lead to the rejection of costs (see Article 42), reduction of the grant (see Article 43), recovery of undue amounts (see Article 44), suspension of payments (see Article 48), suspension of the action implementation (see Article 49) or termination (see Article 50).

22.5.3 Procedure

The Commission will formally notify the beneficiary concerned of the systemic or recurrent errors and its intention to extend these audit findings, together with the list of grants affected.

22.5.3.1 If the findings concern **eligibility of costs**: the formal notification will include:

- (a) an invitation to submit observations on the list of grants affected by the findings;
- (b) the request to submit revised financial statements for all grants affected;
- (c) the correction rate for extrapolation established by the Commission on the basis of the systemic or recurrent errors, to calculate the amounts to be rejected if the beneficiary concerned:
 - (i) considers that the submission of revised financial statements is not possible or practicable or
 - (ii) does not submit revised financial statements.

The beneficiary concerned has 90 days from receiving notification to submit observations, revised financial statements or to propose a duly substantiated alternative correction method. This period may be extended by the Commission in justified cases.

The amounts to be rejected will be determined on the basis of the revised financial statements, subject to their approval.

If the Commission does not receive any observations or revised financial statements, does not accept the observations or the proposed alternative correction method or does not approve the revised financial statements, it will formally notify the beneficiary concerned the application of the initially notified correction rate for extrapolation.

If the Commission accepts the alternative correction method proposed by the beneficiary concerned, it will formally notify the application of the accepted alternative correction method.

22.5.3.2 If the findings concern **improper implementation** or a **breach of another obligation**: the formal notification will include:

- (a) an invitation to submit observations on the list of grants affected by the findings and
- (b) the flat-rate the Commission intends to apply according to the principle of proportionality.

The beneficiary concerned has 90 days from receiving notification to submit observations or to propose a duly substantiated alternative flat-rate.

If the Commission does not receive any observations or does not accept the observations or the proposed alternative flat-rate, it will formally notify the beneficiary concerned the application of the initially notified flat-rate.

If the Commission accepts the alternative flat-rate proposed by the beneficiary concerned, it will formally notify the application of the accepted alternative flat-rate.

22.6 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, any insufficiently substantiated costs will be ineligible (see Article 6) and will be rejected (see Article 42).

Such breaches may also lead to any of the other measures described in Chapter 6.

ARTICLE 23 — EVALUATION OF THE IMPACT OF THE ACTION

23.1 Right to evaluate the impact of the action

The Commission may carry out interim and final evaluations of the impact of the action measured against the objective of the EU programme.

Evaluations may be started during implementation of the action and up to five years after the payment of the balance. The evaluation is considered to start on the date of the formal notification to the coordinator or beneficiaries.

The Commission may make these evaluations directly (using its own staff) or indirectly (using external bodies or persons it has authorised to do so).

The coordinator or beneficiaries must provide any information relevant to evaluate the impact of the action, including information in electronic format.

23.2 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the Commission may apply the measures described in Chapter 6.

ARTICLE 23a — MANAGEMENT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

23a.1 Obligation to take measures to implement the Commission Recommendation on the management of intellectual property in knowledge transfer activities

Beneficiaries that are universities or other public research organisations must take measures to implement the principles set out in Points 1 and 2 of the Code of Practice annexed to the Commission Recommendation on the management of intellectual property in knowledge transfer activities⁶.

This does not change the obligations set out in Subsections 2 and 3 of this Section.

The beneficiaries must ensure that researchers and third parties involved in the action are aware of them.

23a.2 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches its obligations under this Article, the Commission may apply any of the measures described in Chapter 6.

ARTICLE 35 — CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

35.1 Obligation to avoid a conflict of interests

The beneficiaries must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the action is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest ('conflict of interests').

They must formally notify to the Commission without delay any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interests and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.

The Commission may verify that the measures taken are appropriate and may require additional measures to be taken by a specified deadline.

35.2 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 43) and the Agreement or participation of the beneficiary may be terminated (see Article 50).

Such breaches may also lead to any of the other measures described in Chapter 6.

⁶ Commission Recommendation C (2008) 1329 of 10.4.2008 on the management of intellectual property in knowledge transfer activities and the Code of Practice for universities and other public research institutions attached to this recommendation.

ARTICLE 36 — CONFIDENTIALITY

36.1 General obligation to maintain confidentiality

During implementation of the action and for four years after the period set out in Article 3, the parties must keep confidential any data, documents or other material (in any form) that is identified as confidential at the time it is disclosed (**'confidential information'**).

If a beneficiary requests, the Commission may agree to keep such information confidential for an additional period beyond the initial four years.

If information has been identified as confidential only orally, it will be considered to be confidential only if this is confirmed in writing within 15 days of the oral disclosure.

Unless otherwise agreed between the parties, they may use confidential information only to implement the Agreement.

The beneficiaries may disclose confidential information to their personnel or third parties involved in the action only if they:

- (a) need to know to implement the Agreement and
- (b) are bound by an obligation of confidentiality.

This does not change the security obligations in Article 37, which still apply.

The Commission may disclose confidential information to its staff, other EU institutions and bodies or third parties, if:

- (a) this is necessary to implement the Agreement or safeguard the EU's financial interests and
- (b) the recipients of the information are bound by an obligation of confidentiality.

Under the conditions set out in Article 4 of the Rules for Participation Regulation No 1290/2013²⁴, the Commission must moreover make available information on the results to other EU institutions, bodies, offices or agencies as well as Member States or associated countries.

The confidentiality obligations no longer apply if:

- (a) the disclosing party agrees to release the other party;
- (b) the information was already known by the recipient or is given to him without obligation of confidentiality by a third party that was not bound by any obligation of confidentiality;
- (c) the recipient proves that the information was developed without the use of confidential information;
- (d) the information becomes generally and publicly available, without breaching any confidentiality obligation, or
- (e) the disclosure of the information is required by EU or national law.

36.2 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 43).

Such breaches may also lead to any of the other measures described in Chapter 6.

ARTICLE 38 — PROMOTING THE ACTION — VISIBILITY OF EU FUNDING

38.1 Communication activities by beneficiaries

38.1.1 Obligation to promote the action and its results

²⁴ Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 laying down the rules for participation and dissemination in "Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)" (OJ L 347, 20.12.2013 p.81).

The beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner.

This does not change the dissemination obligations in Article 29, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36 or the security obligations in Article 37, all of which still apply.

Before engaging in a communication activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform the Commission (see Article 52).

38.1.2 Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

- (a) display the EU emblem and
- (b) include the following text:

For communication activities: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 688156".

For infrastructure, equipment and major results: "This [infrastructure][equipment][insert type of result] is part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 688156".

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Commission.

This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use.

Moreover, they may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

38.1.3 Disclaimer excluding the Commission responsibility

Any communication activity related to the action must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

38.2 Communication activities by the Commission

38.2.1 Right to use beneficiaries' materials, documents or information

The Commission may use, for its communication and publicising activities, information relating to the action, documents notably summaries for publication and public deliverables as well as any other material, such as pictures or audio-visual material that it receives from any beneficiary (including in electronic form).

This does not change the confidentiality obligations in Article 36 and the security obligations in Article 37, all of which still apply.

However, if the Commission's use of these materials, documents or information would risk compromising legitimate interests, the beneficiary concerned may request the Commission not to use it (see Article 52).

The right to use a beneficiary's materials, documents and information includes:

- (a) **use for its own purposes** (in particular, making them available to persons working for the Commission or any other EU institution, body, office or agency or body or institutions in EU Member States; and copying or reproducing them in whole or in part, in unlimited numbers);
- (b) **distribution to the public** (in particular, publication as hard copies and in electronic or digital format, publication on the internet, as a downloadable or non-downloadable file, broadcasting by any channel, public display or presentation, communicating through press information services, or inclusion in widely accessible databases or indexes);

- (c) **editing or redrafting** for communication and publicising activities (including shortening, summarising, inserting other elements (such as meta-data, legends, other graphic, visual, audio or text elements), extracting parts (e.g. audio or video files), dividing into parts, use in a compilation);
- (d) **translation**;
- (e) giving **access in response to individual requests** under Regulation No 1049/2001²⁵, without the right to reproduce or exploit;
- (f) storage in paper, electronic or other form;
- (g) archiving, in line with applicable document-management rules, and
- (h) the right to authorise third parties to act on its behalf or sub-license the modes of use set out in Points (b),(c),(d) and (f) to third parties if needed for the communication and publicizing activities of the Commission.

If the right of use is subject to rights of a third party (including personnel of the beneficiary), the beneficiary must ensure that it complies with its obligations under this Agreement (in particular, by obtaining the necessary approval from the third parties concerned).

Where applicable (and if provided by the beneficiaries), the Commission will insert the following information:

“© – [year] – [name of the copyright owner]. All rights reserved. Licensed to the *European Union (EU)* under conditions.”

38.3 Consequences of non-compliance

If a beneficiary breaches any of its obligations under this Article, the grant may be reduced (see Article 43).

Such breaches may also lead to any of the other measures described in Chapter 6.

ARTICLE 46 — LIABILITY FOR DAMAGES

46.1 Liability of the Commission

The Commission cannot be held liable for any damage caused to the beneficiaries or to third parties as a consequence of implementing the Agreement, including for gross negligence.

The Commission cannot be held liable for any damage caused by any of the beneficiaries or third parties involved in the action, as a consequence of implementing the Agreement.

46.2 Liability of the beneficiaries

46.2.1 Conditions

Except in case of force majeure (see Article 51), the beneficiaries must compensate the Commission for any damage it sustains as a result of the implementation of the action or because the action was not implemented in full compliance with the Agreement.

Each beneficiary is responsible for paying the damages claimed from it.

46.2.2 Amount of damages - Calculation

The amount the Commission can claim from a beneficiary will correspond to the damage caused by that beneficiary.

46.2.3 Procedure

Before claiming damages, the Commission will formally notify the beneficiary concerned:

- informing it of its intention to claim damages, the amount and the reasons why and
- inviting it to submit observations within 30 days.

If the Commission does not receive any observations or decides to claim damages despite the observations it has received, it will formally notify **confirmation** of the claim for

²⁵ Regulation (EC) No 1049/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2001 regarding public access to European Parliament, Council and Commission documents, OJ L 145, 31.5.2001, p. 43.

damages and a **debit note**, specifying the amount to be recovered, the terms and the date for payment.

If payment is not made by the date specified in the debit note, the Commission may recover the amount:

- (a) by '**offsetting**' it — without the beneficiary's consent — against any amounts owed to the beneficiary concerned by the Commission or an executive agency (from the EU or Euratom budget). In exceptional circumstances, to safeguard the EU's financial interests, the Commission may offset before the payment date specified in the debit note;
- (b) by **taking legal action** (see Article 57) or by **adopting an enforceable decision** under Article 299 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU) and Article 79(2) of the Financial Regulation No 966/2012.

If payment is not made by the date in the debit note, the amount to be recovered (see above) will be increased by **late-payment interest** at the rate set out in Article 21.11, from the day following the payment date in the debit note, up to and including the date the Commission receives full payment of the amount.

Partial payments will be first credited against expenses, charges and late-payment interest and then against the principal.

Bank charges incurred in the recovery process will be borne by the beneficiary, unless Directive 2007/64/EC applies.

Annex 2 - Technical report template

Intermediate Report/Final Report on Extensions	
Acronym of Extension:	
Full Title:	
symbloTe call identification:	
Starting date of the Extension:	
Duration of the Extension:	
Name of Third Party:	

Part A. Summary of the work performed so far

Max 300 words

The information in this section may be used in public documents and reports by the symbloTe consortium

Part B. Detailed description

Describe the achievements so far and the deviation incurred during the implementation for each of the item below.

- B.1 Concept, Objectives, Set-up and Background

Briefly describe the Extension objectives, key deliverables and outputs realized so far.

- B.2 Technical Results

In this section you should describe what and how has been done regarding the different technical/substantial components of the extension

- B.3 Lessons learned

Compare the results achieved against the objectives: clearly assess whether the objectives were met and describe the successes and lessons learned.

- B.4 Impact

Describe Impact that would enhance innovation capacity, create new market opportunities, strengthen competitiveness and growth of companies, or bring other important benefits for society, Potential for technical and commercial application, etc. Describe how the proposed extension has sufficient sustainable benefits for the symbloTe project.

Part C. Resources

- C.1 Resources Deployed

Complete the following table concerning the incurred project costs and comment on each of the cost categories focusing particularly on discrepancies compared to awarded budget. Besides the table below, extra information can be provided to support the requested funding and which may help to judge the cost to the symbloTe project.

Extension Costs Incurred			
Cost category	Budget according to the symbloTe Standard Extension Contract	Costs incurred within the extension duration	%
1. Personnel			
2. Travel			
TOTAL			

- C.2 Further development and exploitation

Describe the plan for further development and exploitation related to the Extension and its successful conclusion and/or beyond the finalization of the collaboration with symbloTe project.

Annex 3 - Specific Extension Contract

SymbloTe Specific Extension Contract

This symbloTe Specific Extension Contract for implementation of the Extension by the Selected Third Party, hereinafter referred to as the “Specific Extension Contract”, is entered into by and between:

INTRACOM SA TELECOM SOLUTIONS (“Cascade Funding Partner”), an organization under the laws of Greece , having its registered office at 19.7km Markopoulou Ave., 19002, Peania, herein represented by ...

And

... (**“Selected Third Party”**), an organization under the laws of ..., having its registered office at , herein represented by ...

Hereinafter sometimes individually or collectively referred to as “Party” or “Parties”.

Whereas the Cascade Funding Partner and the Selected Third Party have agreed the main terms and conditions to implement the Extension in the course of the symbloTe Project by signing the Standard Extension Contract n° **symbloTe ...** which form part of this Specific Extension Contract.

Now therefore it has been agreed as follows:

1. Terms and Conditions for the Extension

The Selected Third Party shall implement the Extension in accordance with the following:

Description of the Extension	
Acronym	
Full Title	
symbloTe Call Identifier	
Starting date of the Extension	
Duration of the Extension	
Date of selection of the Selected Third Party by the Internal Evaluation Committee	

Extension Outcomes	
Expected results in terms of Extension	
Expected results in terms of building blocks, IPs, software and hardware solution	

Implementation of the Extension	
Outline scope of work	
Deliverable 1	<Title of Deliverable>
Description	
Submission Date	
Inputs	
Deliverable 2	<Title of Deliverable>
Description	
Submission Date	
Inputs	
Deliverable 3	<Title of Deliverable>
Description	
Submission Date	
Inputs	
...	...

Information on Background	
symbloTe Background (including imitations and restrictions)	<Background's description here>
Selected Third Party's Background (including imitations and restrictions)	<Background's description here>

Financial Support	
Payment conditions	Scheduled Payments: After the signature of this Agreement, or after the receipt of the appropriate reports (intermediate and final), the Financial Support will be transferred to the Selected Third Party without unjustified delay according to the schedule of payments.
Schedule payments	<p>of</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 40% of the overall financial support as advance payment after the signature of this Agreement with the Coordinator. - 30% of the overall financial support as interim payment based on the evaluation by the symbloTe consortium of the Intermediate Report, edited and provided by Selected Third Party by midterm (after half of the Extension's duration has passed from the Extension starting date). - 30% of the overall financial support as Final payment based on the evaluation by the symbloTe Consortium of Final Report, edited and provided by Selected Third Party at the end of the Extension's duration and (eventually) following a formal approval of the report and the work

	at a Technical Project Review by the EC.
Total Funding for the Extension	- _____ €

Parties involved in the Extension	
Selected Third Party Project Manager	
Full Name & Title	
Organization and Department	
Telephone Number	
E-mail Address	
Cascade Funding Project Manager	
Full Name & Title	
Organization and Department	
Telephone Number	
E-mail Address	
Date of agreement of all the Parties involved in the Extension	

APPENDIX B – Confidentiality and Conflict of Interest Declaration

I the undersigned declare that, in participating as an independent expert in the evaluation of proposals received in the open call of project symbloTe

I undertake to treat as confidential all information contained in the proposals which I am asked to evaluate, both during the evaluation and afterwards.

I will not reveal to any third party the identity or any details of the views of my fellow evaluator(s), neither during the evaluation nor afterwards

I do not, to the best of my knowledge, have any interest in any of the proposals submitted in this call, I have not been involved in their preparation and I do not benefit either directly or indirectly from the eventual selection. Should I discover a conflict of interest during the evaluation, I undertake to declare this and to withdraw from the evaluation.

Name	
Signature	
Date	